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Automated Analysis of Wearable ECG: Machine Learning Methods, Preprocessing Pipelines, and Benchmark Datasets

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Abstract

Wearable and mobile electrocardiography (ECG) has rapidly expanded access to rhythm monitoring outside of clinical settings, but the single- or few-lead nature of these recordings and their susceptibility to motion artefacts complicate clinical-grade interpretation. This review synthesises recent machine learning (ML) approaches for wearable ECG across three problem domains — signal-quality assessment (SQA), single-lead interpretation, and multi-lead interpretation — covering preprocessing pipelines, quality handling strategies, and 18 benchmark datasets. Across studies, no single architectural paradigm consistently outperforms others when evaluated fairly: classical feature-based methods remain competitive for rhythm tasks under resource constraints, while deep discriminative models show stronger cross-database generalisation when training data are sufficient. The most consistent predictor of reported performance is dataset characteristics — particularly scale, demographic composition, and whether signals were acquired from wearable devices in free-living conditions — rather than architectural choice. Three recurring evaluation deficiencies are identified: subject-level data leakage inflating classification metrics, SQA performance reported without acceptance rates, and reconstructed ECG leads validated by waveform similarity alone without downstream diagnostic concordance. A structured comparative summary of all reviewed methods is provided. The analysis clarifies that future progress depends primarily on evaluation rigour, representative datasets, and reproducible preprocessing rather than on architectural novelty alone.

1 Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) remain the leading cause of mortality worldwide, accounting for approximately 32% of all deaths according to WHO [1]. ECG is a core method for measuring cardiac electrical activity, estimated at hundreds of millions of examinations performed annually worldwide [2], and recent growth in wearable and mobile ECG has extended rhythm monitoring into free-living settings, where reduced lead configurations and motion-related artefacts challenge signal validity and downstream automated interpretation. The ECG records the heart's electrical activity at the body surface and remains an indispensable diagnostic tool for detecting rhythm disturbances, conduction abnormalities, and myocardial injury. The standard 12-lead ECG is obtained using ten electrodes placed on the limbs and chest to generate twelve simultaneous projections of the same cardiac electrical events, providing complementary spatial information across the frontal and horizontal planes. Limb leads I, II and III are bipolar and measure the potential difference between pairs of limb electrodes, whereas the augmented unipolar limb leads (aVR, aVL, aVF) employ a single exploring electrode referenced to a combined indifferent terminal, yielding amplified limb projections; the unipolar precordial leads (V1–V6) are chest electrodes that sample the horizontal plane. By capturing multiple vectors of cardiac activity, multi-lead recordings permit localisation of ischaemia, assessment of chamber enlargement and characterisation of complex conduction and repolarisation patterns; in contrast, a single-lead ECG — typically produced by wearable devices — provides only one temporal projection and is therefore principally suited to rhythm monitoring and screening but lacks the multi-vector information required for detailed spatial diagnosis [3]. Although the standard ECG examination remains the primary focus of many studies, a shift towards exercise (stress) testing is observed, with an estimated 20–30 million stress ECG examinations performed annually on a

global scale [4]. This correlates with the parallel increase in use and affordability of wearable devices [5], allowing for a long-period, constant monitoring. Several consumer and medical-grade devices offer clinical-grade accurate ECG sensors to register single-lead signal, which can be used for arrhythmia assessment and at-home ECG analysis [6]. Throughout this review, **wearable ECG** refers to continuously worn body-contact devices that acquire ECG passively during daily life — including chest patches, smartwatch-based single-lead recorders, and textile-integrated electrode systems. **Mobile ECG** refers to hand-held or clip-on devices that require the user to actively initiate a short recording, such as single-lead event recorders and KardiaMobile-class devices. Both categories share the characteristic of reduced lead count and operation outside a controlled clinical setting, but differ in their duty cycle and susceptibility to motion artefact. Previous studies focus on providing a meticulous analysis of: (i) safety and performance of wearable sensors [7], (ii) an in-depth review of signal preprocessing steps, methods and future possibilities [8, 9], (iii) the latest trends of ML-enabled in-home ECG analysis [10], or (iv) focus on the application readiness for both devices, data and algorithms [11, 12]. However, they typically under-emphasise preprocessing–model interactions, signal-quality gating, and evaluation design. This structured review study shows the previously unmentioned research, focusing on the newest takes on wearable ECG signal preprocessing, machine learning methods, applications, most frequently used datasets and on-edge AI aspect, while highlighting challenges related to signal quality and fair evaluation. A novel categorisation framework enables a more accessible overview of ML applications for multi- and single-lead ECG signal analysis in wearable devices.

The main contributions of this publication include:

- A review of computational approaches applied across the ECG analysis pipeline, encompassing preprocessing, learning algorithms and evaluation methodologies.
- Highlighting the most significant advances in recent years in the following domains: SQA, single- and multi-lead ECG automated analysis, covering approaches to signal reconstruction, synthetic signal generation, arrhythmia classification, CVDs classification, and model optimisation for on-edge AI deployment.
- Characterising forthcoming developments in computational ECG analysis, emphasising methodologies applicable to signals obtained from mobile and wearable devices.

2 Scope of work and organisation

This review examines recent computational developments in ECG analysis, with particular emphasis on methods applicable to signals acquired from mobile and wearable platforms as well as conventional multi-lead recordings. We survey techniques spanning the full analysis pipeline — from preprocessing and signal-quality assessment through signal reconstruction and synthetic data generation, to arrhythmia and broader cardiovascular disease classification — paying attention to strategies for model optimisation and deployment on resource-constrained (on-edge) devices. Our aim is to synthesise contemporary methodological trends, identify prevailing datasets and evaluation practices, and to highlight the challenges that must be addressed to enable robust, clinically meaningful use of mobile ECG technology.

Review type and scope declaration

This article is a **structured narrative review**. The literature search and selection were not conducted under a pre-registered protocol, and no claim of exhaustive systematic coverage is made. The review is systematic in its **organisational taxonomy** — studies are consistently grouped by problem domain and methodological paradigm — but the search and inclusion process reflects informed expert judgement rather than a reproducible algorithmic procedure. This framing follows established conventions for narrative reviews in biomedical engineering [8, 9] and is appropriate given the breadth of the topic and the absence of a single standardised outcome measure across the surveyed studies.

Search strategy

Literature was identified through searches conducted between December 2025 and February 2026. Searches combined terms from the following conceptual groups, used in varying two- to four-term combinations:

- *Signal modality*: "ECG", "electrocardiogram", "single-lead ECG", "wearable ECG", "mobile ECG", "ambulatory ECG"

- *Acquisition context*: "wearable device", "smartwatch ECG", "patch ECG", "free-living", "ambulatory monitoring"
- *Method class*: "deep learning", "convolutional neural network", "transformer", "generative adversarial network", "variational autoencoder", "machine learning", "random forest", "support vector machine"
- *Task*: "arrhythmia detection", "atrial fibrillation detection", "signal quality assessment", "ECG denoising", "lead reconstruction", "ECG synthesis", "cardiovascular disease classification"
- *Deployment context*: "on-edge deployment", "embedded ECG", "real-time ECG classification", "model compression ECG", "knowledge distillation ECG"

Representative example queries included: "wearable ECG deep learning arrhythmia detection", "single-lead ECG signal quality assessment machine learning", "ECG lead reconstruction generative adversarial network", "on-edge ECG classification embedded deployment", and "ECG transformer wearable atrial fibrillation". Snowball searching from reference lists of identified review articles [7, 9, 10, 11] was additionally used to identify relevant primary studies.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Studies were included if they: (i) proposed or evaluated a computational method for ECG signal processing, quality assessment, or automated interpretation; (ii) were published in a peer-reviewed journal or as a full conference paper (conference abstracts without an accompanying full paper were excluded); (iii) were written in English; and (iv) were published predominantly after 2020, with earlier seminal works [13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18] retained where they constitute the methodological foundation of the field. Studies were excluded if they: (i) reported only clinical validation of a commercial device without describing the underlying algorithm; (ii) were conference extended abstracts without sufficient methodological detail; or (iii) addressed ECG acquisition hardware design without a signal processing or machine learning component. Dataset and resource papers (Section 8) were included regardless of the above criteria, as their role is to document available benchmarks rather than to propose methods.

Applying these criteria, a total of 65 primary methodological studies and 18 dataset/resource papers were included in the final review. No formal PRISMA flow diagram is provided, as this is a structured narrative review and the search process reflects informed expert judgement rather than a reproducible algorithmic procedure; this limitation is acknowledged.

A structured comparative summary of all reviewed methods — covering best-performing model, reported performance metrics, and on-edge deployment constraints — is provided in Table 1 in the Discussion section. The remainder of the article is organised as follows:

1. **Problem domain** — studies are organised by three problem domains: Signal Quality Assessment (SQA), in which the goal is to assign a quality label to a signal window or recording based on noise level or motion artefact content; Single-lead (SL) ECG interpretation, targeting cardiac state assessment from a single ECG lead; and Multi-lead (ML) ECG interpretation, encompassing CVD classification, signal reconstruction, and signal generation from recordings with more than one channel.
 - **Methods and architectures** — Under each problem domain, published approaches are grouped into three paradigm brackets, organised by the dominant computational role each approach plays in ECG analysis rather than by a strict architectural lineage. This taxonomy is the authors' own proposal and is pragmatic rather than exhaustive: **Classic ML and Advanced Statistical Methods** covers feature-engineered, interpretable pipelines — K-Nearest Neighbours (K-NN), Support Vector Machines (SVM), Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM), Linear/Logistic Regression (LR), Decision Trees (DT), and related ensemble methods — where model inputs are hand-crafted descriptors of signal morphology or statistics; **Deep Discriminative Models** covers end-to-end supervised neural networks principally trained for classification or regression on raw or minimally processed signals, including Convolutional (CNN), Recurrent (RNN), and Residual (ResNet) architectures; **Attention-based and Generative Architectures** groups methods whose defining characteristic is either attention-driven sequence modelling or learned signal generation and reconstruction — including Transformer encoders, self-supervised pre-training frameworks, Variational Autoencoders (VAE), and Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN). It should be noted that this grouping is use-case oriented:

Transformer-based architectures can be discriminative, and indeed several reviewed papers use them purely for classification; they are placed in the third category because their dominant role in the wearable ECG literature surveyed here is sequence modelling, representation learning, and reconstruction — contexts in which they are typically contrasted with GANs and VAEs rather than with CNNs. VAEs and GANs are co-located in this subsection not because they share an architecture but because they share a functional role in ECG pipelines: both are applied to signal synthesis, missing-lead imputation, and data augmentation. Readers should be aware that this grouping does not imply architectural equivalence between these model families.

2. **Preprocessing** - the goal of this section is to provide a map across commonly used approaches to tackle noisy signals and improve data quality, common steps and patterns in data transformation pipeline, feature extraction and multi-modality handling.
3. **Data Quality Handling** - describes common behavioural patterns and methods of dealing with data of lacking quality.
4. **Datasets** - a separate section dedicated to exploring most popular and latest ECG datasets. Data availability played a role of a separating factor, where datasets were labelled to be either open-source, on-demand (usually upon contacting the author) or closed. Together with a brief instruction on accessing the signals, a summary of the dataset is provided to the reader for easier usefulness assessment.

Together, these sections provide a self-contained reference for researchers and practitioners seeking to deploy ECG analysis on resource-constrained wearable platforms, from algorithm selection through to dataset access. The overall structure is summarised in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Tree diagram of the article organisation as described in Section 2. Studies are grouped by top-level categories: (i) signal quality assessment, (ii) single-lead ECG interpretation, and (iii) multi-lead ECG interpretation, each further organised by method paradigm; (iv) preprocessing pipeline; (v) data quality handling; and (vi) datasets.

3 Signal quality assessment(SQA)

Signal Quality Assessment plays a key role in successful application of abnormalities detection algorithms, improving final solution capacity, positively affecting the training process, i.e. removing signal windows where information is malformed by the noise or movement artefacts, and by increasing final vote confidence, as only signals of high quality are analysed. Community challenges provide widely used benchmarks and taxonomies of "too noisy to classify" recordings. The PhysioNet/CinC 2011 Challenge focused on algorithms that can run on mobile phones to provide feedback during acquisition [15], and the PhysioNet/CinC 2017 Challenge explicitly includes a noisy class in short single-lead recordings [13], reinforcing the practical need to integrate SQA with classification pipelines.

3.1 Classic ML and Advanced Statistical Methods

In their recent work, You et al. [19] frame signal quality assessment as a decision fusion problem rather than a single-model classification task. Therefore, instead of trying one-fits-all approach, they

propose an ensemble of four complementary classifiers purposed for ECG signal quality assessment algorithms — k-Nearest Neighbours, AdaBoost, Naïve Bayes, and Random Forest — each trained independently, with fusion rules learned separately to combine their outputs. Decisions are based on inputs formed from measured wavelets entropy and energy, concatenated with additional signal kurtosis. This multi-classifier fusion model is characterised by dynamic fusion rules learned during independent training phases of each classifier where fusion rules for the multi-classifier ensemble are determined. Random Forest algorithm was employed by Tan et al. on an ECG signal acquired from a custom smart mattress during both simulated sleep and real-time sleep experiments [20]. The experiments were carried out, with a difference in the assigned quality ranges (1-5 or 0-10). The input to the algorithm was delivered as single-channel, 5 s long ECG segments, based on which the 26 feature long vector was computed. Although the SQA task may be treated as a scoring challenge performed on the whole recording, Olejarczyk et al. [21] focused on finding and localising stochastic noise artefacts within the ECG signal. In their study authors performed extensive testing of 34 different classifiers out of which the classifier derived from an optimised ensemble RUSBoosted Trees algorithm delivered the best results. Manually annotated artefacts served as a ground truth for the performance evaluation. Input features vector included outcomes of non-linear analysis which used measures such as approximate entropy, sample entropy, Higuchi fractal dimension, Detrended Fluctuation Analysis and Katz fractal dimension. The dataset comes from a cohort study where about 8 hours of ECG single-lead signal was collected from participants during sleep using a Movesense ECG device. Noise artefacts detection and classification using Light GBM was demonstrated by Moon et al. [22]. Their approach used 45 features selected out of 553 identified features using Recursive Feature Elimination, and was trained on the proprietary KURIAS ECG database with tests and validation performed on open datasets. Rahman et al. [23] present a knowledge-based framework for ECG denoising that first detects whether noise is present, then classifies the noise type, to finally apply a corresponding conventional filter to avoid altering already clean segments. The machine-learning component uses a hierarchical, feature-based ensemble approach, with AdaBoost chosen as the primary model for both noise detection and multi-class noise classification. Algorithm turns superior in comparison with other classical classifiers such as SVM and tree-based methods. The approach relies on handcrafted dynamic and statistical features extracted from short ECG windows and examines how resampling to a common sampling rate influences feature separability and model performance.

3.2 Attention-based and Generative Architectures

Liu et al. [24] introduce LEAF-Net, a lightweight attention-based architecture for fine-grained ECG signal quality classification. The model combines multi-scale convolutional feature aggregation with multi-head self-attention and efficient channel recalibration, and natively supports joint ECG and PPG input streams. Validated on over 573 hours of wearable recordings from more than 9000 patients, LEAF-Net achieves fine-grained quality scores in close agreement with expert labels while remaining suitable for real-time wearable deployment. Edder et al. [25] propose ECGDnet, a Transformer encoder-based architecture that recasts EMG denoising as a sequence-modelling task, using learnable positional embeddings and a composite MSE+L1 training objective to preserve fine waveform morphology. On a benchmark against convolutional baselines, ECGDnet achieves an SNR of 19.83 dB, NMSE of 0.0158, and a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.9924 against clean reference signals. The authors suggest suitability for resource-constrained settings, although no hardware benchmarks, model size figures, or inference latency measurements are reported — a gap that limits direct assessment of edge deployability. Nguyen and Phan [26] propose CMA-ECG, a cross-modal attention framework that fuses the raw ECG signal with free-text noise descriptions and the latent representations of a pre-trained LLM (GPT-3, LLaMA-2, T5, or BERT) to jointly perform quality classification and denoising in a single architecture. The multi-task framing allows textual noise characterisation to actively steer signal processing, positioning CMA-ECG as a step towards language-aware ECG analysis. No hardware benchmarks are reported, and edge deployability is not discussed. Hu et al. [27] propose a multi-task Transformer framework that performs quality assessment, noise localisation, and denoising simultaneously under a joint loss, rather than treating them as sequential stages. The encoder follows the Vision Transformer paradigm, treating ECG segments as patch tokens, and is trained with intra-class awareness to handle heterogeneous noise within a single quality category. Weak supervision on abnormal data further improves robustness, and the joint architecture produces spatially interpretable noise masks alongside cleaned signals.

Alghieth [28] proposes DeepECG-Net, a hybrid CNN–Transformer architecture with integrated attention-based denoising, targeting real-time arrhythmia detection. The model achieves 98.2% precision, 96.8% recall, and a 97.5% F1-score, and is validated on a Raspberry Pi 4B with a 30 MB

footprint and sub-50 ms inference latency. A federated training extension is included to address regulatory constraints on sharing raw patient ECG data across devices.

3.3 Deep Discriminative Models

Wearable ECG quality degradation is characterised by non-stationary artefacts — motion bursts, intermittent electrode lift-off, and muscle noise — whose spectral and morphological signatures overlap substantially with the cardiac signal itself. Fixed-threshold or hand-crafted feature methods struggle to capture this variability across devices and activity contexts, whereas convolutional and hybrid deep architectures can learn to identify device- and cohort-specific corruption patterns directly from annotated waveform data, without requiring explicit feature engineering. Fu et al. [29] compared classical margin-based models (SVM, LS-SVM) and sequence models (LSTM) for wearable ECG quality assessment using Lenovo H3 recordings, while also contrasting performance with challenge-style data collected using wet electrodes. In an occupational setting, Abreu and Silva used segment-level signal quality indices (SQIs) and a Random Forest classifier to assess ECG quality in a firefighter-oriented wearable scenario, leveraging the naturalistic ScientISST MOVE dataset [30, 31]. Mondal et al. [32] use the first-order derivative ECG as input to a compact CNN quality classifier, systematically sweeping 60 architectural configurations across convolutional depth, kernel size, and activation function. The optimal configuration achieves 97.59% accuracy, 98.78% sensitivity, and 89.23% specificity on two unseen databases, at a model size of 2,989 kB. Deployment on a Raspberry Pi confirms a 130.44 ms inference time per 5-second window, establishing real-time feasibility for on-device quality gating. Kalousková et al. [33] address the problem of identifying unreadable segments in long-term wearable ECG, reframing it as a four-class CNN classification task using dual parallel inputs — the raw time-domain signal and its FFT amplitude spectrum. The frequency stream is shown to be essential: no tested architecture exceeded 40% validation accuracy on raw signal alone. The model achieves 87.62% accuracy in a three-class formulation and 98.70% for the clinically critical binary decision of whether heart rate is detectable, with an inference time of 48 ms per 2-second segment. Rakshit and Maity [34] extend SQA from binary clean/noisy labelling to a five-class taxonomy distinguishing low-, high-, and mixed-frequency noise alongside unacceptable segments, allowing quality labels to directly inform noise-specific denoising. The compact CNN backbone (435 kB) achieves F1-scores of 95.93% and 94.20% on two unseen databases (PCCC-2011 and PCCC-2021), demonstrating cross-database generalisation. Raspberry Pi deployment confirms real-time feasibility at 510 ms per 2-second segment.

4 Single-lead ECG interpretation

Single-lead ECG interpretation has gained considerable clinical and research attention with the proliferation of wearable and consumer-grade devices — such as smartwatches and handheld recorders — capable of acquiring lead I or modified limb lead configurations. Exemplar procedure of smartwatch signal acquisition is presented on Figure 2. While single-lead recordings impose inherent constraints on diagnostic information compared to standard 12-lead systems, they offer a practical trade-off between signal richness and acquisition simplicity, making them particularly relevant for continuous ambulatory monitoring. The studies reviewed in this section span tasks including arrhythmia classification, atrial fibrillation detection, ischaemic and structural cardiovascular disease assessment, physiological parameter estimation, and signal reconstruction — collectively illustrating the expanding clinical scope of single-lead wearable platforms.

4.1 Classic ML and Advanced Statistical Methods

Feature-engineered pipelines remain attractive for on-device constraints and interpretability. For example, in age estimation from smartwatch ECG, Adib et al. evaluate a range of feature-based regressors and report strong performance for tree-based ensembles, relying on hand-crafted temporal and spectral descriptors [35]. Marzoog et al. [36] conducted a single-centre observational study of 80 participants, validated against CT myocardial perfusion imaging as the reference standard, examining whether parameters extracted from a single-lead ECG recorded with the proprietary Cardio-Qvark device — captured both at rest and immediately after physical exertion — could support detection of ischaemic heart disease (IHD). In this study, bicycle ergometry yielded an AUC of 50.7% for IHD detection, while LASSO regression applied to single-lead ECG features achieved an AUC of 67%, with better specificity. The difference between modalities did not reach statistical significance, which the authors attribute to the limited sample size. These results should be interpreted cautiously: the cohort of 80 participants is insufficient to draw generalisable conclusions about the relative diagnostic value of ergometry versus wearable ECG, and the findings motivate rather than establish the case for validation in larger, multicentre cohorts. Angelaki et al. [37] address hypertension classification using

Figure 2. Image of Single-Lead ECG acquisition using Garmin Venu 3 smartwatch.

a Random Forest trained on features from a single ECG lead derived from a standard 12-lead clinical recording, supplemented by patient demographic features. This study does not use a wearable device; it is included here as methodological context for single-lead classification of non-rhythm CVD targets, where the lead-derived signal simulates the information available to a wearable. The authors demonstrate that a single-lead representation, while less information-rich than the full 12-lead recording, retains sufficient discriminative signal for a binary hypertension classification task. In order to find the most suitable lead for AF prediction, Choi et al. [38] tested dedicated models for nine individual leads, as three augmented leads were excluded, coming to conclusion that the model trained on lead-I delivered the best performance. The architecture of choice was a modified Light Gradient Boosting Machine which was trained to perform binary prediction of AF. To provide all necessary information to the model, 60 features vector is constructed based on characteristics that are extracted from 10 seconds of single-lead signal, which were additionally joined together with patients demographics. Data comes from long-running proprietary study conducted at Samsung Medical Center between January 2010 and December 2021, and external validation data comes from Wonju Severance Hospital. Marzoug et al. [39] investigate whether single-lead ECG features can serve as a non-invasive proxy for metabolic syndrome (MetS) diagnosis in a single-centre prospective study of 80 participants. A Random Forest classifier trained on 47 ECG-derived features achieved moderate performance; adding clinical features substantially improved results, though all findings require cautious interpretation given the limited sample size. The study establishes that MetS produces detectable electrical changes in single-lead ECG, motivating validation in larger cohorts.

4.2 Attention-based and Generative Architectures

To address the information loss of single-lead wearable ECG, generative models have been explored to reconstruct multi-lead signals. Yoon et al. [40] generated 12-lead ECG from lead I using a U-Net-based GAN trained on hospital ECG data, and evaluated feasibility via downstream tasks. Complementary to synthesis, clinical protocols for obtaining multiple sequential "virtual" leads with a smartwatch have been proposed, demonstrating that by repositioning the device, it can approximate Einthoven and Wilson-like leads [41, 42]. Presacan et al. in [43] evaluate the mathematical accuracy of reconstructed 12-lead ECGs from single- or dual-lead inputs using a GAN trained on the PTB-XL cohort. Student's t-test and F-test were used to assess differences in signal means and variances respectively. The results indicate a regression-to-the-mean effect: the model's outputs converge towards a population-average morphology rather than reproducing patient-specific waveform features, meaning that individually distinctive characteristics — such as T-wave polarity, ST amplitude, or QRS axis — are smoothed out in the reconstruction. Adding a second input lead did not significantly improve signal recreation, suggesting that the model's limited personalisation capacity is the primary constraint. Kapsecker et al. [44] use disentangled representational learning in the proposed Variational Autoencoder based approach for interpreting single-lead ECG recordings to

perform anomaly detection. Autoencoder’s ability to filter out irrelevant signal disruptions while preserving and isolating subtle features relevant to anomalies allowed to enhance model robustness, increasing personalisation and mitigating inter-subject variations. Among advantages like being largely unsupervised, authors highlight the explainability aspect of the proposed model. Ikram et al. [45] propose a hybrid pipeline for multi-class ECG arrhythmia recognition in which classical preprocessing and feature engineering feed a Transformer-based classifier. The preprocessing stage performs denoising, normalisation, and relabelling, followed by correlation-driven feature pruning, handcrafted feature engineering, and PCA-based dimensionality reduction; t-SNE is used to verify class separability in the refined feature space. The Transformer operates on this engineered feature representation rather than on raw signal, making the architecture a feature-based Transformer rather than an end-to-end deep model. The authors note that real-life deployment in a resource-constrained setting would require additional optimisation, but provide no hardware benchmarks or latency measurements to characterise the gap between the reported model and an embedded implementation. Approach targeting long-term dependencies hidden within the 1D signal similar to [28] is presented by Premanand et al. [46]. By combining CNNs capability to focus at local feature extraction and the ability to capture far-reaching temporal dependencies innate to multi-head self-attention based algorithms, a novel, deep learning ECG-ResViT architecture, outperforming several existing state-of-the-art methods, comes to light. The authors emphasise the potential for real-time deployment in conjunction with clinical applications; however, no hardware benchmarks, model size figures, or inference latency measurements are reported to substantiate this claim, limiting direct assessment of practical deployability. Hempel et al. [47] introduce a domain-guided attention mechanism constraining a 1D-ResNet to predefined waveform intervals — P-wave or QRS complex — rather than the full beat, embedding physiological knowledge directly into training. When attention is directed to the diagnostically relevant interval performance is preserved; when misdirected, it degrades — providing interpretable, physiology-grounded learning without sacrificing accuracy. Applied retrospectively to Apple Watch recordings from decompensated HFrEF patients, beat-level arrhythmia burden derived from the model predicted 3-month rehospitalisation and cardiovascular mortality.

4.3 Deep Discriminative Models

Briosa e Gala et al. [48] compared automated AF classification from Apple Watch Series 6 and Skylabs CART Ring single-lead recordings against cardiologist-adjudicated 12-lead reference rhythms in 483 patients across three centres (2398 ECGs total). The CART Ring achieved sensitivity 84.6% and specificity 89.9% with a 1.9% unclassified rate, versus a substantially higher unclassified rate for the Apple Watch. Physician interpretation improved accuracy for AF and sinus rhythm but remained limited for other arrhythmia types; the specific classification algorithm is not disclosed. Against this clinical backdrop, much of the recent methodological work on wearable ECG classification has centred on deep learning. Efficient 1D convolutional architectures have been trained for arrhythmia detection directly from smartwatch ECG, with validation spanning both wearable datasets and canonical benchmarks such as MIT-BIH [49, 14]. Where model size is the binding constraint, knowledge distillation offers a principled path forward — transferring performance from a large teacher network to a compact student suitable for embedded hardware [50]. Robustness to real-world acquisition conditions is the central concern of the CARE-I framework, which targets lead I recordings captured in free-living environments [51]. For atrial fibrillation specifically, DNN-based analysis has been shown to improve detection from smartwatch ECG in clinical cohorts [52], while more recent work extends this further — identifying AF signatures within otherwise normal sinus rhythm recordings [53] and predicting near-term AF onset from mobile ECG databases [54]. A distinct architectural challenge is the gap between 12-lead training data and single-lead deployment. Safdar et al. [55] address this through a hierarchical framework in which a CNN augmented with dedicated translational layers, trained on 12-lead ECG data, is adapted to classify single-lead signals — exploiting the morphological richness of institutional 12-lead archives to bootstrap classifiers for the leaner wearable modality. Meisenzahl et al. [56] develop a supervised 1D CNN to classify 10-second single-lead wearable ECG segments as AF versus non-AF, with subject-level generalisation enforced by holding out out-of-distribution subjects for validation and testing. AF recurrence is defined as three consecutive positive 10-second segments. Quantitative classification performance is not publicly disclosed in the accessible version of this work. The same challenge is tackled by [57] where authors present K-B2S+ architecture, a 1-D CNN designed for AF detection from short single-lead ECG recordings acquired by wearable devices. The proposed architecture employs five CNN blocks with progressively decreasing kernel sizes (from 75 to 3) combined with inter-block feature concatenation to mitigate feature loss during training. But while CNNs excel at analysing characteristic spatial

signal features, they may struggle with temporal dependencies [58]. Recurrent neural networks with their inherent ability to capture temporal dependencies allow the algorithm to focus on the changes stretched in the time domain. Such signal evolution is used as a base information in an early warning detection method for arrhythmias proposed by Li et al. [59]. Self-supervised learning based feature extraction builds an input vector provided to LSTM-based network. Recurrent networks, however, tend to score worse than CNNs when it comes to local patterns and spatial hierarchies [60]. To combine benefits of both, and minimise related drawbacks, researchers explore the potential of combined/hybrid architectures, often joining convolutional neural networks with recurrent neural networks like gated recurrent unit or bidirectional long short-term memory. Wei et al. [61] evaluated such hybrid residual recurrent convolutional neural net in a multi-label diagnosis task. Tested on a proprietary dataset from Shanghai First People’s Hospital Affiliated to Shanghai Jiao Tong University, their solution dominated other state-of-the-art implementations.

5 Multi-lead ECG interpretation

Multi-lead ECG recordings provide complementary spatial projections of cardiac electrical activity, enabling localisation of ischaemia, characterisation of conduction abnormalities, and assessment of chamber enlargement that single-lead signals cannot support. Exemplar 12-lead ECG recording is shown on Figure 3. This additional spatial information extends directly to machine learning: multi-lead inputs allow models to exploit inter-lead correlations and spatial–temporal dependencies, potentially improving classification performance for CVDs whose manifestations are distributed across multiple cardiac vectors.

Figure 3. Exemplar 12-lead ECG recording with significant signal power jump on one of the electrodes.

5.1 Classic ML and Advanced Statistical Methods

Twelve-lead ECG remains the standard clinical acquisition format, and feature-engineered classifiers applied to these recordings benefit from the rich spatial information available across all leads. In Japan, routine paediatric ECG screening generates high volumes of recordings requiring specialist interpretation; Sugitani et al. [62] evaluate ten machine learning algorithms for classifying key feature representations from such recordings, with CatBoost achieving the best performance in terms of both specificity and recall. Improved SVM applied to implantable ECG sensor is a proposition of Patchamatla et al. [63] to support continuous patient monitoring with a focus on effective atrial fibrillation (AF) detection. Proposed classifier is equipped with Radial Base Function kernel. Data was recorded from 29 patients with AF. Preprocessing includes isolation of the QRS complex, leveraging signal-processing procedures that include wavelet-transform-based analysis with Daubechies wavelets and statistical feature characterisation. On this basis, the proposed pipeline links feature extraction to supervised classification to distinguish rhythm patterns associated with

AF. Kilic et al. [64] provide further evidence for the competitiveness of gradient boosting methods: their LightGBM model outperformed a 1D CNN in specific arrhythmia classification based on features derived from signal morphology and HRV, while the CNN operated on raw segmented signal. Models were evaluated on 3-channel Holter ECGs from the Dokuz Eylül University Heart Rhythm Management Centre (DEUHRMC) dataset, which is available from the corresponding author. Kolliyil et al. [65] demonstrate the potential of gradient boosting based methods applied to multi-lead ECG analysis. Based on 654 individual features, covering both statistical-, time-, frequency- and wavelet-based characteristics, authors apply eXtreme Gradient Boosting framework to classify each recording into 9 diagnostic classes, scoring particularly well in detecting Left Bundle Branch Blocks. During Training phase, an ensemble learning was applied on gradient boosting of decision trees. Both [62], [64] and [65] use Shapley Additive Explanations to increase explainability of the solution by visualising feature contributions. Looking for an alternative to using Gradient Boosting based methods, one may find work of Chauhan et al. [66], where Bundle Branch Block detection is the study subject, and 5th-order Tensor Domain Machine Learning is the tool of choice. To prepare an input vector Multivariate Fast Iterative Filtering decomposes each 12-lead beat into local components, after which the Continuous Wavelet Transform is applied to the resulting modes to obtain their time–frequency representation. The suggested method demonstrated almost perfect accuracy scores for distinguishing healthy signals from left-, right- bundle branch blocks. To combine benefits of classic ML methods and deep learning, Karampour et al. [67] propose a hybrid approach for early diagnosis of cardiac ischemia. Input data vector is computed by additionally including deep learning-based features provided by CNN or RNN model’s outputs. To assign importance and assess informativeness of said features, the novel solution utilising self-organising map-based feature extraction method is proposed. Classification performance is measured with multiple classic classifiers, where SVM coupled with inputs from CNN demonstrated the best results, slightly outperforming the same classifier provided with RNN-based features.

Across these studies, several common patterns emerge. Gradient boosting methods (CatBoost, LightGBM, XGBoost) are consistently the top-performing classic ML paradigm for multi-lead ECG classification, appearing in four of the six reviewed studies and outperforming other classical classifiers in each case. Explainability is a recurring priority: three studies [62, 64, 65] employ SHAP-based feature attribution, reflecting the clinical requirement for interpretable decisions. However, a significant methodological limitation shared across this group is the reliance on single-institution datasets without external validation. The reported performance figures — while high — cannot be confidently attributed to the algorithmic approach rather than to favourable dataset characteristics. Furthermore, cohort sizes are generally small (29 to several hundred subjects), and none of the reviewed studies report calibration metrics or positive predictive values under realistic prevalence conditions, which limits the translation of these results to clinical practice.

5.2 Attention-based and Generative Architectures

Commonly faced issue across many machine learning research is the problem of unbalanced datasets, which has tremendous impact on results achieved. This is particularly true for automated solutions applied in healthcare, as these rare, seldom faced abnormalities, when under-represented in the dataset, may often be completely ignored by the algorithm. To tackle the challenge of lacking data, resampling of the dataset may be performed, increasing the presence of previously marginalised cases, or synthetic data may be derived from the original signal, creating a new, partially artificial yet representative input [68]. Transformers and GAN-based architectures, are used widely in tasks of creation artificial texts, images or objects and, in the biological measurement domain, they are used as generators of synthetic or transformed recordings including missing or incomplete signal pieces. Ismail et al. [69] focus on the aforementioned problem of under-represented rare arrhythmias, proposing a GAN for minority class augmentation applied to multi-lead ECG recordings from three open-source datasets. Authors readjust the class distribution with GAN-generated samples before training a classifier on the balanced set. The proposed method demonstrates the capability to accurately generate multi-lead electrocardiogram recordings of rare arrhythmias, allowing for significant improvements in classifier performance, surpassing previous state-of-the-art solutions. By repositioning an Apple Watch to the ankle and chest to simulate leads II, V1, and V6, Ploux et al. [70] demonstrate the capability to significantly expand the diagnostic reach of single-lead smartwatch ECG beyond atrial fibrillation and bundle branch block detection. While standard wrist recording (lead I) performs well for AF and complete bundle branch block, the four-lead configuration substantially improves detection of atrial flutter, AV block, repolarisation abnormalities, and pathological Q-waves — findings that are systematically missed when confined to a single vector. This work provides clinical evidence that consumer-grade wearables can approximate multi-lead

diagnostic utility through deliberate lead placement, without any hardware modification. The 12-lead electrocardiogram apparatus delivers significantly more processable information than simpler wearable devices. The drawback however is the lack of portability, where wearable sensors allow for constant patient monitoring, not affecting their daily routines in a life-changing manner. To bridge the informational gap between the two, Guan et al. [71] propose a Variational Autoencoder-based method, named WearECG, to reconstruct the complete screening, based on the signals from three leads: II, V1, and V5 recorded by a wearable device. By focusing on enhancing model capacity to detect temporal and spatial dependencies, architecture demonstrated improvements in generation quality metrics. Additionally, to deepen validation of diagnostic utility, a pre-trained ECGFounder model was fine-tuned and evaluated on execution multi-class classification on over 40 different CVDs. The approach shows promising potential of applying generative modelling for biological signal reconstruction. Rather than synthesizing missing leads, reduced-lead classification adapts high-performing 12-lead architectures. González-Cabeza et al. studied 3-lead vs. 12-lead ECG classification on PTB-XL and adapted a state-of-the-art 12-lead model, showing that reduced-lead setups can preserve much, but not all, of the 12-lead performance [72]. An attempt to allow lead-aware decision was made by Niloy et al. [73] in their study, where MuRe-LAT, a multi-resolution, lead-aware transformer based model, with domain adaptation was implemented and trained for arrhythmia classification. Compared to ResNet-1D, BiLSTM, ECG-BERT, and CardioFormers, MuRe-LAT overcome most of them, offering a balanced alternative between accuracy and efficiency. Despite the widespread adoption of digital acquisition systems, paper ECG printouts remain the most historically prevalent format for clinical ECG documentation, with vast legacy archives still inaccessible to automated analysis without dedicated digitisation pipelines [74]. Thus, challenges arise to treat multi-lead analysis not only in terms of signal processing, but image processing as well. Duranay et al. [75] bridge these two approaches, transforming 12-lead ECG signal recordings into PNG data which is later analysed with Visual Transformer based algorithm. During the extensive model evaluation with various model architectures and employing six different Class Activation Mapping techniques to enhance interpretability, ViT-B/384 delivers the best performance outperforming current state-of-the-art approaches utilising CNNs with both high accuracy and F1-measure.

5.3 Deep Discriminative Models

Before reviewing studies with direct wearable relevance, it is useful to establish the performance benchmarks set by large-scale 12-lead clinical ECG work, which defines the architectural templates and diagnostic expectations against which wearable methods are implicitly compared. These studies do not involve wearable devices and are included as historical context rather than as subject-matter coverage. Ribeiro et al. [76] trained a deep neural network on over two million labelled 12-lead exams from the Telehealth Network of Minas Gerais and demonstrated that a DNN could classify six categories of ECG abnormalities at a level exceeding cardiology residents. Hughes et al. [77] extended this to a multi-label 38-class setting and applied the LIME explainability technique to identify which ECG segments drove each classification decision. Together, these works establish both the architectural templates and the performance ceiling that inform transfer learning and benchmarking efforts when the problem shifts to reduced-lead or wearable contexts, where training data are scarcer and signal fidelity inherently lower. The authors of [78] present a dedicated ECG coprocessor designed for on-chip arrhythmia detection, addressing two persistent limitations of existing hardware — poor energy efficiency and fixed-function architectures. By pairing a zero-crossing adaptive threshold R-peak detector with a reconfigurable 1D-CNN classification engine, and fabricating the design in 55 nm CMOS, the chip achieves competitive classification accuracy while consuming substantially less energy than comparable CNN-based ECG processors, with the added flexibility of supporting variable lead configurations and field-updatable inference models. Wrist-worn device signal recordings served as a test set for Janciuleviciute et al. [79] where ECG-Based detection of Acute Myocardial Infarction was the challenge. The classification task was tackled with two types of models: a CNN operating on raw 4-lead signal as input and a gradient-boosting decision tree, where clinically informative features were provided as a decision basis. Across the study, CNN proved to outperform the decision tree based model. CNN structure consists of 3 repeated convolutional blocks of 1D CNN which are flattened at the end, with the Softmax function delivering the final score. Additional explainability is provided by using Grad-CAM. The feasibility of deriving multi-lead configurations from a smartwatch was established by Samol et al. [41], who showed that repositioning an Apple Watch across six electrode locations yields signals of good diagnostic quality, with correct lead allocation confirmed in all Einthoven and 92% of Wilson-like recordings. Avila et al. [42] provided an early clinical proof of concept in two ED

patients with STEMI, where a repositioned Apple Watch faithfully reproduced the ST-elevation pattern confirmed by catheterisation. Spaccarotella et al. [80] subsequently validated the approach in 100 participants across STEMI, NSTEMI, and healthy controls, reporting sensitivity and specificity exceeding 90% for both conditions. Most recently, Choi et al. [81] introduced an AI layer to this workflow, applying a deep learning tool to ECG images from both standard and smartwatch recordings to generate probability scores for STEMI, ACS, and myocardial injury. The resulting diagnostic scores showed high concordance between the two modalities, with AUROC values for ACS detection that were statistically indistinguishable, suggesting that the diagnostic gap between standard and smartwatch-derived recordings can be substantially closed through AI-assisted interpretation. As cardiovascular diseases may often coexist, or the symptoms may be common across multiple ones, Hryniów et al. [82] introduce a multi-branch RNN-based model to solve a multi-label, multi-class classification challenge. Aside from wavelet decomposition, temporal- and frequency-based features, a separate input stream, termed the domain-knowledge representation, is provided, with domain-specific indices like McPhee-, Sokolov-Lyon-, Cornell-, Romhilt- and Lewis-index computed for each signal window. The inclusion of domain-knowledge features improved performance, allowing LSTM and GRU based architectures, previously demonstrating inferior results, to achieve parity with CNN state-of-the-art solutions. Another CNN approach is demonstrated by Kim et al. [83] where authors evaluate a CNN-based STEMI classifier operating on 12-lead ECG images rather than raw waveform data, demonstrating non-inferior diagnostic performance to joint clinical evaluation by emergency physicians and cardiologists. The image-based input design is a deliberate pragmatic choice — by operating on printed ECG scans, the system remains deployable on existing hardware without requiring AI-enabled acquisition devices, improving real-world scalability. Several contributions explicitly consider on-device inference. Rahman et al. [84] designed a resource-constrained wearable ECG system and evaluated latency and power alongside classification performance, illustrating that model choice and preprocessing (e.g., beat windowing) interact strongly with embedded constraints. Related efficiency strategies include compact CNN designs [49] and knowledge distillation for student models [50].

6 Preprocessing

Preprocessing constitutes a foundational stage in any ECG analysis pipeline, directly conditioning the reliability of all downstream processing steps. Across the studies reviewed, preprocessing encompasses signal formatting, temporal alignment, and unit standardisation - tasks whose implementation details vary considerably between publications, yet whose correctness is a prerequisite for reproducible and clinically translatable results.

6.1 Signal Formatting

Preprocessing strategies reported across ECG SQA studies share several common elements — baseline wander suppression through high-pass filtering, band-limiting to suppress electromyographic interference, and fixed-length windowing to support segment-level quality decisions — yet their specific implementation choices vary considerably. Reported cutoff frequencies, window lengths, and definitions of unacceptable quality differ substantially across publications, complicating direct cross-paper comparisons [29, 32, 30]. Mondal et al. [32] adopt the derivative ECG signal (dECG) as their primary input representation, a choice intended to emphasise beat-level morphological dynamics and suppress low-frequency artefacts prior to convolutional processing. At the opposite end of the complexity spectrum, Abreu and Silva [30] demonstrate that SQA for wearable firefighter ECG can be achieved using as few as eight handcrafted cardiac features, yielding 88% accuracy and an 87% F1 score — an important finding for resource-constrained deployment scenarios where full signal processing pipelines are impractical. More stringent quality gating is reported by Meisenzahl et al. [56], who explicitly discard segments with amplitude exceeding 3 mV or signal energy greater than 3 standard deviations above the mean, and apply a bandpass filter with a 0.5 Hz low-frequency cutoff combined with a 50 Hz notch filter to suppress powerline interference. Deep learning pipelines for wearable ECG classification typically impose standardised formatting — fixed sampling rates, fixed-length segments, and amplitude normalisation — often supplemented by augmentation strategies such as additive noise injection, synthetic oversampling, or time-warping to improve robustness to acquisition variability [50, 51, 57]. For beat-level arrhythmia classification, centring segments on detected R-peaks is a widely adopted strategy to reduce sensitivity to variable heart rate [84]. The precision of this upstream step directly conditions downstream classification reliability: Rahman and Morshed [84] report their on-chip QRS detection algorithm achieves a 99.5% F1 score with an R-peak position error of 6.3 ms. For noise suppression, discrete wavelet transforms are widely employed; Safdar et al. [55] report that the bior3.1 wavelet performed well for ECG denoising

in their single-lead context, though wavelet selection is dataset- and task-dependent and this finding should not be generalised without independent replication. When the classification target is risk inference from normal sinus rhythm, careful PQRST-centred segmentation and precise label definition are particularly important to avoid shortcut learning from device-specific signatures or residual artefacts [53, 54].

6.2 Signal Alignment

ACS-oriented pipelines that operate on ECG images or multichannel recordings acquired through sequential smartwatch repositioning introduce additional preprocessing demands beyond those of single-channel systems: lead alignment, temporal synchronisation across sequentially captured channels, and consistent measurement of ST deviations relative to an isoelectric reference. The transparency with which these steps are reported varies considerably in the literature, yet both Spaccarotella et al. [80] and Choi et al. [81] highlight that documenting this process explicitly is essential for reproducibility and clinical translation. Feature-based methods are inherently sensitive to beat delineation quality, since errors in R-peak detection propagate directly into HRV descriptors, morphological features, and spectral power estimates. Accordingly, such pipelines require explicit R-peak detection, cardiac cycle segmentation, and robust normalisation prior to feature computation [35, 29]. In free-living settings, these steps can become failure points unless tightly coupled with upstream signal quality assessment.

6.3 Unit Conversion

Presacan et al. [43] report a practically motivated unit conversion step: although signal samples are originally stored in millivolts (mV), they are rescaled to microvolts (μV) before being passed to the MUSE 12SL commercial analysis system, which accepts inputs only in that unit. While the conversion has no bearing on the generative model's performance, it is a prerequisite for the downstream feature extraction performed by the MUSE system — a reminder that integration with proprietary clinical tools can impose format constraints that are orthogonal to, yet inseparable from, the signal processing pipeline itself.

7 Data Quality Handling

One of the most popular approaches to handling insufficient data quality is quality-based filtering ranging from interpretable statistical rules to learned quality classifiers. In all cases, the role within the pipeline is the same: to gate which signal segments proceed to downstream analysis and which are discarded or flagged for noise-aware treatment.

7.1 Threshold-Based Exclusion

The most transparent approach applies fixed thresholds directly to signal statistics. Jančiulevičiūtė et al. [79] implement a sequential gating pipeline: following zero-phase bandpass filtering between 0.5 and 100 Hz, beats whose energy exceeds the 90th percentile of the within-recording distribution are discarded. A subsequent template-matching step retains only beats whose correlation coefficient with the recording average exceeds 0.5, and any recording yielding fewer than 10 accepted beats is rejected in its entirety. Meisenzahl et al. [56] apply analogous exclusion rules at segment level, discarding any window with peak amplitude exceeding 3 mV or signal energy more than 3 standard deviations above the mean, after applying a 0.5 Hz high-pass and 50 Hz notch filter.

7.2 Synthetic Signal Generation

Filtering, however, reduces the available data for the algorithm to train at, which may pose further difficulties like class imbalance. To tackle such challenge of imbalanced dataset, the authors of [24] employ a simple formula described in eq. (1) and eq. (2) to generate a synthetic signals.

$$\text{signal}_{\text{synthesis}} = \text{signal}_{\text{raw}} + \lambda \times \text{signal}_{\text{noise}} \quad (1)$$

$$\lambda = \sqrt{10^{-\frac{R}{10}} \times \frac{P_{\text{raw}}}{P_{\text{noise}}}} \quad (2)$$

where $\text{signal}_{\text{synthesis}}$ denotes the unacceptable signal synthesised, formed by combining the original signal $\text{signal}_{\text{raw}}$ with a noise segment $\text{signal}_{\text{noise}}$ drawn from the target database and scaled by λ . In eq. (2), P_{raw} is the power of the raw physiological signal and P_{noise} is the power of the selected noise segment. For each synthesis trial, either the *ma* or *em* noise record is chosen at

random, one of the two leads is randomly selected, and the extraction start time within the noise record is randomised.

Addressing the fundamental challenge of dataset imbalance and data scarcity in ECG-based model training, several generative approaches have been proposed to augment minority classes with physiologically plausible synthetic signals. Adib et al. [35] systematically compared multiple GAN-family architectures for synthetic Normal-class ECG beat generation from the MIT-BIH arrhythmia dataset, introducing a structured evaluation framework based on DTW, Fréchet, and Euclidean distance metrics alongside a novel productivity-rate concept to quantify the proportion of morphologically acceptable generated beats. The same group further investigated whether state-of-the-art 2D probabilistic diffusion models (Improved DDPM) could be adapted for 1D ECG synthesis via a Gramian Angular Field embedding pipeline, ultimately finding that WGAN-GP consistently produced higher-quality, more realistic beats across all evaluated metrics [85]. Complementarily, [86] proposed a hybrid data-balancing strategy combining NearMiss undersampling of the majority class with WGAN-GP-based synthetic oversampling of minority classes, demonstrating that such a pipeline can yield a well-balanced training set with substantially improved minority-class representation across all five arrhythmia categories of the MIT-BIH dataset.

7.3 Feature-Based Quality Scoring

Where fixed thresholds are insufficient, a richer quality representation can be constructed from handcrafted features and passed to a classifier. Tan et al. [20] define a 26-dimensional feature vector spanning time-domain statistics (RMS energy, crest factor, kurtosis, skewness, morphological length, among others), frequency-domain descriptors (spectral entropy, centre frequency, mean squared frequency), auto-correlation based periodicity measures, established SQIs (baSQI, pSQI, eSQI, rsdSQI), R-wave amplitude and interval statistics, and an average template correlation coefficient — the output of which determines whether a segment is admitted to downstream processing. Fu et al. [29] demonstrate that a more compact set of non-morphological features - approximate entropy, sample entropy, fuzzy measure entropy, the Hurst exponent, kurtosis, and power spectral density — is sufficient for reliable quality gating of wearable ECG, while Abreu and Silva [30] show the same binary decision can be reached with as few as eight cardiac features in a demanding firefighter monitoring scenario.

7.4 Learning-Based Quality Filtering

End-to-end learned methods replace explicit feature engineering with representations derived directly from the signal. Mondal et al. [32] use the derivative ECG (dECG) as input to a convolutional quality classifier, using morphological dynamics to flag segments unsuitable for further processing. Liu et al. [24] extend this to fine-grained, real-time quality labelling across multiple physiological signal streams from wearable devices, allowing downstream models to selectively use only sufficiently clean windows. Kalousková et al. [33] produce a segment-level interference mask from a CNN, enabling partial exclusion within a recording rather than wholesale rejection. Where noise type can be identified — as in Rakshit and Maity [34], who distinguish five quality categories including low-, high-, and mixed-frequency noise — the quality label directly informs which noise-specific denoising strategy is applied, rather than simply triggering exclusion. Hu et al. [27] and Nguyen and Phan [26] take this further by integrating quality assessment and denoising within a unified preprocessing architecture, allowing the two tasks to inform one another rather than operating sequentially.

8 Datasets

8.1 Established Open-Access Benchmarks

In order to provide the reader with a complete field view, we include descriptions of the most popular datasets, which often serve as a point of comparison across proposed methods and algorithms. Although they are not new, their impact on the field is continuously proving to be of vital significance. All datasets mentioned, are available as open-source databanks.

- **AliveCor single-lead [13]:** Single-channel signals between 30 to 60 seconds long consumer-recorded ECGs labelled for normal rhythm, atrial fibrillation, other rhythm, and noise for the PhysioNet/CinC 2017 Challenge.
- **CPSC2018 (China Physiological Signal Challenge 2018) [87]:** Public 12-lead ECG database from the China Physiological Signal Challenge 2018 for rhythm/morphology abnormality detection across multiple diagnostic classes.

- **PTB-XL [17]:** Large clinical 12-lead ECG dataset (10s recordings) with cardiologist annotations and rich metadata, designed as a benchmark for ECG ML and evaluation protocols.
- **CinC 2011 [15]:** PhysioNet/CinC 2011 dataset of short 12-lead ECGs with human quality grades, used to develop algorithms for real-time ECG quality feedback on mobile devices.
- **MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database [16]:** Classic benchmark of 2-channel ambulatory ECG excerpts with detailed beat/arrhythmia annotations for evaluating arrhythmia detectors and rhythm analysis methods.
- **INCART 12-lead Arrhythmia Database [18]:** A PhysioNet-hosted set of 75 annotated 30-minute 12-lead Holter ECG recordings (257Hz) from 32 patients, with >175k beat annotations, collected in the context of coronary artery disease evaluation.

8.2 Novel ECG Datasets

With the growing popularity and accessibility of wearable devices, more and more curated datasets are being published providing either single-lead ECG, combination of multi-lead wearable sensors with clinical registration or a multi-modal setup, where not only ECG is provided, but secondary devices provide synchronised auxiliary signals. Where datasets are open-access or available on request, they are described to support reproducibility. Closed or proprietary datasets are included only where they were used in studies reviewed in the preceding sections; their inclusion here serves to document the data conditions under which those results were obtained, not to recommend them as community benchmarks. Readers should note that closed datasets preclude independent replication.

- **ScientISST MOVE:** The multi-modal dataset ScientISST MOVE [31] published by Saraiva et al. provides ECG, EMG, PPG and EDA recordings from subjects performing physical activities. The data was gathered from three independent wearable devices, a chest band, an arm band, and an Empatica E4 wristband. Total of 17 healthy subjects were analysed during data acquisition sessions, yielding an average of 37 minutes of usable, synchronised recordings across all sensors. With characterisation of the effects of daily activities on physiological signal acquisition process in mind, the ScientISST MOVE dataset is a valuable source of aligned, multi-modal data, which can be also used in signal quality assessment tasks.
- **Open-Access Arrhythmia Database of Wearable Electrocardiogram:** An Open-Access Arrhythmia Database of Wearable Electrocardiogram by Shen et al. [88] is an open-access arrhythmia database derived from wearable multi-lead ECG recordings in realistic ambulatory conditions, intended to support the development and validation of automatic ECG analysis algorithms. Data was collected using a 6-lead wireless ECG monitor from over 200 patients with heart disease, and two curated resources were created. First of them is a signal quality database with ten-second segments labelled into three quality levels, second of them being an arrhythmia database with thirty-second recordings covering a range of sinus, atrial, and ventricular arrhythmias with expert annotations. The database is integrated into a cloud-based platform that manages data acquisition, storage, expert labelling, and automated ECG analysis (including preprocessing, QRS detection, and CNN-LSTM-based classification), providing a comprehensive benchmark for research on wearable ECG quality assessment and arrhythmia detection.
- **The BUTQDB:** The BUTQDB [89] dataset from Brno University of Technology was created by Nemcova et al. to assess ECG signal quality and includes long-term single-lead ECG and 3-axis accelerometer recordings from 15 people aged 21–83, collected during everyday activities in 2018–2019. Data were recorded with a Bittium Faros 180 device at 1,000 Hz for ECG and 100 Hz for accelerometer signals, with recordings lasting at least 24 hours. The quality of the ECG is classified into three classes, ranging from clearly readable signals (Class 1) to unsuitable signals for analysis due to unreliable QRS detection (Class 3). The dataset is split into training and test groups by participant IDs, and in this work Classes 2 and 3 are combined as poor quality while Class 1 is considered good. Overall, the dataset provides 15,659 labelled 20-second segments.
- **Childhood Cancer Survivors:** An open dataset containing both clinical 12 lead ECG and paired apple watch single lead electrocardiogram data was published by Akbilgiac et al. [90]. Dataset contains paired recordings from 243 adult childhood cancer survivors were signals were collected during same clinical visit allowing side-by-side comparison of both signals, captured within a short time interval, where on average time interval between captures was around 42

minutes \pm 18 min. Data is available via open Github repository where .npy and .csv files are exposed.

- **Kurath-Koller 2025:** ECG collected from two separate mobile devices: Apple Watch and KardiaMobile 6L was compared to clinical recordings by Kurath-Koller et al. [91] in a dataset available on demand upon contacting the corresponding author. Database consists of signals collected from 30 young individuals. Mobile device was consistently used as the right-arm electrode, however by changing placement of the device on patient's body, authors were able to record not only lead I, but lead II, III, aVR, aVL, aVF and V1-V6 as well. Article contains description on how to position the device in order to obtain desired lead recording which is undoubtedly useful in reproducing results.
- **wECGdb:** The wECGdb [92] dataset contains paired, simultaneously recorded two-lead wrist-worn ECG (wECG) and reference 12-lead ECG from 92 adult participants recruited at Vilnius University Hospital Santaros Klinikos (Lithuania), designed for developing and testing 12-lead synthesis from wearable recordings. Wearable signals were acquired at 500 Hz, while the 12-lead ECG was recorded at 200 Hz and resampled to 500 Hz; both modalities were filtered with a 0.5 Hz high-pass Butterworth filter and a 100 Hz low-pass Parks-McClellan low-pass filter, and wearable recordings were quality-screened using a consensus beat-detection signal-quality index with additional beat replacement by an amplitude-scaled average beat. Data are distributed as 92 per-participant MATLAB .mat files containing metadata and site-specific structures with availability flags (and training/testing segments for guided recordings), plus a spreadsheet with participant characteristics and diagnoses.
- **PhysioCGM:** Multimodal dataset named The PhysioCGM is an open, ambulatory multimodal collection designed to support non-invasive glucose analytics, collected by Quamer et al. [93] with a particular emphasis on raw wearable ECG: participants wore a Zephyr BioHarness chest strap providing continuous ECG waveforms sampled at 250 Hz over extended free-living periods. Pair these ECG recordings with synchronised wrist-worn PPG (64 Hz) and EDA (4 Hz) from Empatica E4 and Dexcom G6 CGM glucose values every 5 minutes, allowing ECG-centric modelling as well as multimodal fusion approaches. The release includes both human-readable raw files and timestamp-aligned, CGM-anchored 5-minute clips (e.g., ECG segments matched to glucose timestamps), facilitating supervised ML experiments for glycemic event prediction while preserving high-resolution cardiac dynamics relevant to glycemic changes.
- **The FOSTER:** First ever publicly available collection of simultaneously recorded forcecardiography (FCG), seismocardiography (SCG), phonocardiography (PCG), reference respiration, and a reference Lead II ECG, intended to support research on integrated electrical and mechanical cardio-respiratory monitoring is called The FOSTER [94] dataset and is available in an open-access. It comprises recordings from 40 healthy participants (20 male, 20 female), with each session lasting approximately 7 minutes and including both quiet breathing and brief inspiratory/expiratory apnea phases, yielding about 280 minutes (roughly 4.7 hours) of synchronised multimodal data in total. All channels, including the ECG, were acquired synchronously with high temporal precision (10 kHz sampling, 16-bit), enabling accurate alignment of ECG-derived cardiac timing with mechanical and acoustic cardiac signatures.
- **Jeppesen 2025:** Jeppesen et al. in the study [95] report a prospective multicentre evaluation of continuous wearable ECG for real-time seizure detection, using expert-reviewed video-EEG as the diagnostic reference and providing seizure time-points aligned to the wearable recordings. The primary biosignal is a single-lead (Lead II) wearable ECG acquired with the Cortrium C3 Monitor patch and streamed via Bluetooth to a smartphone (Google Pixel 4a) for on-device R-peak detection and heart-rate-variability analysis. In total, the study accrued 3530 hours of streamed wearable ECG during the test period, including 880 hours from the autonomic-change-eligible subgroup (median 56.5 hours per eligible patient), with 42 annotated seizures in 17 eligible patients. For reuse, the authors state that the HRV-based detection algorithm is open source for non-commercial use, and that de-identified participant-level data including the wearable ECG signals, gold-standard seizure time-points, and basic demographics will be shared upon request for scientific non-commercial purposes for 10 years post-publication. Data access is therefore via direct request to the study team as specified in the paper's data-sharing statement, rather than through an automatic public download repository.

- **Closed Marzooq 2025 dataset:** A proprietary study performed in [36] uses a plethora of data sources, including various stress metrics like watts and metabolic equivalents, as well as vascular indices, hemodynamic averages, echocardiographic ejection fraction, estimated vessel age, creatinine and estimated glomerular filtration rate. ECG recordings come from 12-lead clinical ECG hardware. To obtain single-lead recordings used for classification, Cardio-Qvark single-lead portable recorder is used.
- **Closed ZioXT dataset:** Study of 89 patients (older than 60 years) undergoing transthoracic electrical cardioversion, followed by continuous 14-day ambulatory monitoring using the ZioXT single-lead ECG patch (199.8 Hz sampling; 1 μ V amplitude resolution) was used as a data source for algorithm evaluation in [56]. Rhythm labelling is based on technician review (M12A software), with 5% of records independently reviewed by a board-certified cardiologist for quality assurance, and AF episodes are defined as lasting at least 15 s with annotated start/end times.
- **Pre-/Post-STEMI ECG:** The University of Michigan pre-/post-STEMI ECG dataset [96] comprises paired digital 12-lead ECG recordings collected from patients discharged from Michigan Medicine between 2016 and 2021 with a diagnosis of acute ST-elevation myocardial infarction. For each individual, the dataset includes a single ECG acquired more than one week prior to the index STEMI event and a single ECG acquired more than one week after the event, alongside associated demographic information and longitudinal clinical outcomes, including mortality and heart failure. Motivated by the difficulty of prognostic modelling in the post-STEMI setting—particularly with respect to incident heart failure—the dataset was curated to support analyses of temporal changes in cardiac electrical activity. As such, it constitutes a valuable resource for developing and benchmarking non-invasive risk stratification approaches aimed at characterising heart-failure severity and progression in post-STEMI populations.

9 Discussion

The literature surveyed in this review highlights a recurrent pattern: performance gains in wearable and mobile ECG analysis are frequently driven less by classifier architecture and more by how studies operationalise *signal validity* and manage the constraints of limited-lead acquisition (Sections 3 to 7). In particular, the methodological fault lines occur at (i) the interface between signal quality assessment and downstream inference, (ii) the choice of modelling paradigm (classic, deep discriminative, or generative/transformer-based) under real-world noise, and (iii) the evaluation design and dataset representativeness (Section 8). Below, a synthesis of said themes and an outline of implications is provided for aligned studies. Table 1 provides a structured cross-study comparison of all reviewed methods, covering model category, reported performance metrics, and on-edge deployment constraints, enabling direct inspection of the patterns discussed in the subsections that follow.

Table 1: Comparative summary of ECG analysis studies: best-performing model, reported performance scores, evaluation metrics used, and on-edge deployment constraints.

Reference	Best Model	Best Model Scores	Evaluation Metrics	On-Edge Deployment Constraints
Signal Quality Assessment				
[19]	Multi-classifier fusion (parallel ensemble of AdaBoost, Random Forest, k-NN, and Naive Bayes; majority-vote fusion with Random Forest as tie-breaker)	Acc 96.49%, Se 99.68%, Sp 85.56%	Accuracy (Acc); Sensitivity (Se); Specificity (Sp)	Evaluated on a desktop PC (Intel Core i5-7400 @ 2.60 GHz, 4 GB RAM, MATLAB 2017b); no inference latency, model size, power consumption, or embedded deployment reported.

Continued on next page

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Reference	Best Model	Best Model Scores	Evaluation Metrics	On-Edge Deployment Constraints
[20]	26-feature Random Forest (RF classifier + RF regressor)	Acc 81.0%, Se 77.5%, P+ 75.5%, F1 76.4%, AOA 99.1%; RMSE 1.17, R 0.935, APICP 90.2% (2-Off)	Accuracy; Sensitivity; Precision; F1-score; Acceptable Overlap Accuracy (AOA); RMSE; Pearson R; Acceptable Prediction Interval Coverage Probability (APICP)	No hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power consumption, model size) reported
[21]	Optimized Ensemble RUSBoosted Trees	Se 99.8%; Sp 73.7%; PPV 99.8%; NPV 74.3%; Acc 99.6%	Sensitivity; Specificity; Precision (PPV); Negative Predictive Value (NPV); Accuracy	Explicitly targeted at single-channel wearable ECG; model size 53 MB and inference speed 20,000 obs/s reported; no on-device deployment demonstrated; authors note Discriminant classifier (5 kB, 2 s training) preferable for memory-constrained wearables at the cost of lower specificity (59.5%)
[22]	LightGBM	Binary detection: F1 89.88% (internal); multiclass (5 artifact types): avg. F1 88.35% (internal), 94.35% on CinC2011, 92.70% on MIT-BIH NST (external, unseen)	Accuracy; Sensitivity; Specificity; AUROC; F1-score; MCC; AUPRC (per artifact subclass)	Feature extraction time 0.343s/sample; LightGBM inference 0.018s/sample on desktop (Intel i7-12700, 64 GB RAM); no embedded or wearable hardware benchmarks reported; real-time deployment planned but not yet implemented.
[23]	Hierarchical AdaBoost	Noise detection: Acc 99.82%, Se 99.27%, Sp 99.94%, F1 99.88%; Noise classification (average): Acc 97.15%, Sen 95.49%, Sp 97.90%, F1 95.65%; Noise-profile filtering: mean QT difference = 2.50 ms, mean QRS difference = 4.28 ms	Accuracy; Sensitivity; Specificity; F1-score; Bland-Altman mean difference for QRS and QT intervals	No hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power, model size) reported
[25]	ECGDnet - encoder-only Transformer	SNR 19.83 dB, NMSE 0.0158, PCC 0.9924 (denoising, MIT-BIH + synthetic sEMG noise)	SNR (dB), NMSE, Reconstruction Error (RE), Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC)	No hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power, model size) reported.
[26]	CMA-ECG (cross-modal attention + LLaMA-2 7B; dual cross-lead and temporal attention encoder)	AUC 96.42%, Acc 90.83%, F1 86.51% (quality assessment, BUT-QDB); MSE 0.0591, SL1 0.0304 (denoising, MIT-BIH NST); ROUGE-L 0.747, METEOR 0.777 (perturbation description, MIMIC-IV-ECG)	AUC, ACC, Precision, Recall, F1-score (quality assessment); MSE, MAE, Smooth-L1 (denoising); BLEU-4, METEOR, ROUGE-L, CIDEr-D (perturbation description)	Requires NVIDIA A100 GPU; 7B-parameter LLM backbone precludes direct wearable deployment; no hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power, or model size for edge targets) reported;

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Reference	Best Model	Best Model Scores	Evaluation Metrics	On-Edge Deployment Constraints
[27]	Multi-task Transformer (Seq2Seq; Conv patch embedding + MHSA encoder $\times 6$ + decoder $\times 3$; three task heads: denoising, SQA, noise localization)	Weighted avg. F1 95.72%–98.49%, Acc $>95.68\%$; SNR improved from -1.95 ± 3.83 dB to 12.20 ± 2.51 dB under severe noise; CosSim 0.98 ± 0.02 (denoising, BUT)	Precision, Recall, F1-score, Accuracy, AUC (SQA); SNR improvement (dB), PRD (%), RMSE (mV), CosSim (denoising)	Original: 1.31 M params, 4.99 MB, 62.84 M MACs, 5.21 ms latency (Intel i7 CPU); after pruning + INT8 quantization: 0.25 M params, 0.25 MB, 3.02 ms latency with $<3\%$ accuracy drop; validated for real-time edge deployment
[29]	LSTM	TPR 98.66%, TNR 86.65%, Se 97.47%, Acc 96.73%	True Positive Rate; True Negative Rate; Sensitivity; Accuracy	Dataset collected on Lenovo H3 wearable device (dry + wet electrodes, Bluetooth transmission, 400 Hz, 12-bit); no inference latency, model size, power consumption, or edge deployment benchmarks reported
[30]	Random Forest (RF) with stratified 5-fold cross-validation on 8 hand-crafted ECG features	Acc 87.85%; Pr 91.75%; Re 84.42%; F1-score 86.63% (10 s segments, 50% overlap)	Accuracy; Precision; Recall (Sensitivity); F1-score	No hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power, model size) reported
[32]	Lightweight 1D CNN with first-order derivative ECG (dECG) input	Acc 97.59%; Se 98.78%; Sp 89.23%	Accuracy; Sensitivity; Specificity	Model size 2,989 kB; inference latency 130.44 ± 46.24 ms for 5 s ECG on Raspberry Pi (ARM Cortex-A72, 8 GB RAM); no power consumption reported
[33]	CNN with dual input: raw ECG (time-domain) + FFT amplitude spectrum	Acc 87.62%, F1 87.62% (3-class: readable / partially readable / unreadable); Acc 98.70%, F1 98.70% (binary: heart rate detectable vs. non-detectable)	Accuracy; Precision; Recall; F1-score (per class and aggregated)	Average inference latency 48 ms per 2 s segment on MacBook Pro 2019 (Intel Core i5, 16 GB RAM); 3.97 M parameters; no model size (MB) or power consumption reported; edge suitability noted but embedded deployment not yet validated
[34]	Lightweight 1D CNN	F1-score 98.05% on MIT-BIHA; 95.93% on unseen PCCC-2011; 94.20% on unseen PCCC-2021	F1-score (average, per-class); unseen-database generalization	Model size 435 kB; average inference time 510.19 ms per segment on Raspberry Pi; no power consumption reported
Single-Lead ECG Interpretation				
[35]	Feedforward Neural Network	Age estimation MAE 2.93 years; binary age classification accuracy 93–97% (thresholds 13–21 years)	MAE; SDAE; Pearson's r ; Accuracy; TPR; TNR; F1-score	Fitbit Sense smartwatch (250 Hz); all inference off-device; no on-device hardware benchmarks reported
[36]	XGBoost gradient boosting classifier with LASSO-based feature selection	AUC 67.0% (95%CI: 53.1%–80.2%); Se 51.6% (95%CI: 33.3%–69.5%); Sp 75.5% (95%CI: 62.8%–88%); NPV 0.712; PPV 0.571;	AUC; Sensitivity; Specificity; NPV; PPV	Single-lead ECG acquired via CardioQvark device. No hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power, model size) reported.

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Reference	Best Model	Best Model Scores	Evaluation Metrics	On-Edge Deployment Constraints
[37]	Random Forest	AUC 83.1% (95% CI: 78.1%–87.1%); Acc 75%; Se 72%; Sp 82%	AUC; Accuracy; Sensitivity; Specificity	Lead I isolated from clinical 12-lead ECG, not a native wearable recording; no hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power, model size) reported.
[38]	LightGBM (Bayesian-optimised; 60 morphological + HRV features per lead)	AUROC 87.2% (internal); AUROC 80.1% (external); Se 82.6%; Sp 64.2%; F1 75.6% (external, Lead I)	AUROC; Sensitivity; Specificity; PPV; NPV; F1-score	Lead I isolated from clinical 12-lead ECG (Philips PageWriter, 500 Hz), not a native wearable recording; no hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power, model size) reported
[39]	Random Forest (47 SLECG-derived features; Cardio-Qvark device)	ECG-only RF: AUC 60.3% (95 % CI: 44%–76.6%), Accuracy 58.8%, F1 42%	AUC-ROC; Accuracy; Precision; Recall; F1-score; Brier score	Single-lead ECG acquired with Cardio-Qvark; no hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power, model size) reported
[40]	U-Net-based conditional GAN (12-lead generation) + ResNet (classification)	Generated 12-lead: mean Pr 82%, Re 80%, F1 81%; vs. real Lead I: Pr 70%, Re 0.72%, F1 70%	Precision; Recall; F1-score (per class and mean)	No hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power, model size) reported
[43]	GAN - UNet-based encoder-decoder with patch discriminator	RMSE 76-136 μ V across precordial leads; $R^2 \leq 0.49$ for amplitude reconstruction; regression-to-the-mean demonstrated for all leads ($p < 0.05$); dual-lead input did not significantly improve reconstruction	RMSE; R^2 (amplitude correlation); Bland-Altman bias and limits of agreement; Student's t-test (means); F-test (variances)	Designed for single-lead wearable input (Lead I); no hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power, model size) reported
[44]	β -TCVAE with 12-dimensional disentangled latent space + kNN classifier	F1 94% (binary: sinus vs. pathology); F1 93% (3-class: NSR/PAC/PVC); accuracy 90.94%	F1-score; accuracy; sensitivity; specificity	No hardware benchmarks, model size, or inference latency reported
[45]	Transformer (multi-head self-attention, 4 heads)	Acc 97.1%; F1-score 95%; AUC 96% (validation set, single dataset, no external validation); APC recall 100% but precision low; Fusion Beat correctly classified in only 52.5% of cases (confusion matrix)	Accuracy; F1-score; AUC; per-class Precision, Recall; Confusion matrix	No hardware deployment; cloud-based training only; authors explicitly state inference latency, computational requirements, and hardware feasibility were not evaluated
[46]	ECG-ResViT	Acc 99.13%; Pr 99.15%; Re 99.13%; F1 99.13%; ROC-AUC 99.94%	Accuracy; Precision; Recall; F1-score; ROC-AUC	No hardware deployment; authors explicitly acknowledge ViT quadratic attention complexity $O(T^2N)$ precludes wearable/edge deployment without further optimisation; no inference latency or model size benchmarks reported

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Reference	Best Model	Best Model Scores	Evaluation Metrics	On-Edge Deployment Constraints
[47]	1D-ResNet with domain-guided single-head attention	External validation (PTB-XL): AF AUC=97.9%, 1dAVb AUC=94.7%, RBBB AUC=99.1%, LBBB AUC=99.5%.	AUROC, F1, Sensitivity, Specificity; 5-fold CV on CODE; external validation on PTB-XL, Georgia, CPSC-2018; Spearman ρ for XAI-feature correlation.	Model runs on Apple Watch Series 7 data but inference is offline/retrospective, not on-device. N=32 smartwatch cohort is a proof-of-concept only; No edge hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power consumption, or model size) reported.
[48]	CART Ring cloud-based proprietary algorithm — clinical validation vs. Apple Watch Series 6 (on-device)	Se 84.6%; Sp 89.9%; unclassified rate 1.9%	Sensitivity, Specificity, PPV, NPV, Accuracy (95% CI); Cohen's K; worst-case and lenient scenarios; McNemar's test.	No edge hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power consumption, or model size) reported. Apple Watch on-device; CART Ring cloud-based.
[49]	1-D CNN (binary and multiclass modes)	Acc 99.57%, Se 99.57%, Sp 99.47%, F1 99.57%, AU-ROC 99.58%. On the smartwatch (Simband) binary task: Acc 64.81%, Se 89.47%, Sp 6.25%	Accuracy, Sensitivity, Specificity, F1-score, AUROC (with 95% bootstrap CI reported for both)	1.2M parameters, 68.48 MFlops reported for the binary model. No actual deployment performed, no hardware target is named. Training required no GPU (20–30 min on CPU).
[51]	Adaptive Lead-Weighted ResNet denoted as DCNN	AUC 91.5%, Se 86.7%, Sp 85.8% (clean lead I, GA dataset); minimum external validation AUC 80.7% across three datasets	AUC (per-arrhythmia); Sensitivity; Specificity	Designed for smartwatch lead I ECG (10 s, 500 Hz); validated on simulated free-living noise (BW, EM, WGN at 0 dB SNR) only — no actual smartwatch recordings used for training or testing; no hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power, model size) reported
[52]	Cardiologs DNN - a two-network pipeline: U-Net CNN + VCG-Like CNN	Se 91% (95% CI: 85-95%); Sp 95% (95% CI: 91-97%); inconclusive rate 1% vs. 19–25% for Apple's native algorithm	Sensitivity; Specificity; inconclusiveness rate	Inference is cloud-based (server-side), not on-device. Wave detector: 800K parameters; rhythm classifier: 4M parameters. Authors explicitly acknowledge that the on-device Apple algorithm has lower compute but higher inconclusive rate, and that a custom SW-trained model would likely outperform.
[53]	1D ResNet50	Test set: AUC 0.79, F1 71.9%, Re 79.3%, Pr 65.8%, Acc 70.5%; external validation (72-hour Holter): AUC 0.68, F1 64.1%, Re 68.9%, Pr 60.0%, Acc 63.4%	AUC; F1-score; Recall (Sensitivity); Precision; Accuracy	Single-lead mobile ECG acquired via mobiCARE-MC100 device (256 Hz, 60 s recordings); no hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power, model size) reported.

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Reference	Best Model	Best Model Scores	Evaluation Metrics	On-Edge Deployment Constraints
[54]	Vision Transformer (ViT) pretrained on MIMIC-IV-ECG (12-lead) via Masked Autoencoder	Limb lead model: AUC 78.4% (7-day), 77.4% (14-day), 77.3% (31-day); lead I model: AUC 72.3%, 72%, 67.1% respectively; limb lead model significantly outperforms lead I model across all time frames ($p < 0.001$, DeLong's method)	AUC (with 95% CI)	No hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power, model size) reported.
[57]	K-B2S+ (1-D CNN; three-module architecture)	Acc of 93.8%, Se of 84.3%, Sp of 92.1%, Overall F1-score: 85.4%	F1-score (per class + mean), Sensitivity, Specificity, Accuracy, 10-fold cross-validation reported	No specific wearable hardware target is named in the paper.
[55]	Sequential 2D CNN	Lead I (best): Acc 81.77%, AUROC 0.81, Se 76.60%, Sp 83.44%;	Accuracy; AUROC; Sensitivity; Specificity	Designed for smart-watch lead I SL-ECG (AliveCor, 300 Hz); model size 2.56 MB with 0.37M parameters; requires intermediate compute stage (authors suggest Nvidia Jetson Nano class device) as model cannot run directly on edge hardware; no inference latency or power consumption benchmarks reported
[58]	Ensemble of CNN + CNN-LSTM + Transformer features fused via concatenation, classified by majority voting (SVM, LR, RF)	Acc 99.56%; Pr: 99.82%; Re: 98.87%; F-score: 99.34%	Accuracy; Precision; Recall; F-score	No hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power, model size) reported; authors note the model requires GPU deployment due to computational intensity of three parallel deep learning branches
[59]	Pretrained 1D-ViT combined with dual state features and 2-layer LSTM	PAF: Acc 93.7%, Se 96.2%, Sp 87.9%, mean lead time 18.9 min (on 111 test records); VF: Acc 98.6%, Se 97.4%, Sp 100%, mean lead time 2.9 min (on 70 test records)	Accuracy; Sensitivity; Specificity; Warning lead time (T_a); Harmonic metric (HM)	Warning model deployed on a cloud platform connected to a wearable ECG patch; LSTM hidden states stored server-side between 10 s windows; no inference latency, power consumption, or on-device model size reported
[60]	Ensemble of BiLSTM + 2×LSTM (base classifiers) fed into a final 1D CNN-LSTM network.	Se 94.52%; Sp 96.42%; Acc 95.45%	Sensitivity; Specificity; Accuracy	No hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power, model size) reported.
Multi-Lead and 12-Lead ECG Analysis				
[62]	CatBoost with measurement-based features only	Sp 85.9% (95% CI: 67.1%–92.1%) at fixed Re: 96%; Acc 90%; Pr 82.1%; NPV 0.970; PR-AUC: 96.6% (95% CI: 94.8%–98.3%)	PR-AUC; Specificity at fixed recall (96%); Accuracy; Precision; NPV; ROC-AUC; 95% CI via 1,000 bootstrap resamples	No hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power, model size) reported

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Reference	Best Model	Best Model Scores	Evaluation Metrics	On-Edge Deployment Constraints
[64]	LightGBM classifier with SHAP explanations	AUROC 99.3% (95% CI: 99%–99.6%); Acc 98.39%; Pr up to 99.90%	AUROC; Accuracy; Precision; Recall; F1-score	No hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power, model size) reported; tested on workstation (Intel Core i7, 16 GB RAM, NVIDIA GTX 1080)
[65]	XGBoost classifier	Weighted F1 68%, MCC 0.64; best per-class external F1 AF 79%, RBBB 77%, LBBB 76%, IAVB 73%; mean AUC-ROC: 0.92	Accuracy; Precision; Recall; F1-score (macro and weighted); MCC; AUC-ROC per class (9 classes: NORM, AF, IAVB, LBBB, RBBB, PAC, PVC, STD, STE); SHAP value analysis for feature interpretability	CPU-compatible (no GPU required); lightweight and potentially deployable on low-resource hardware; no hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power consumption, or model size) reported
[66]	FOTDML: Fifth-Order Tensor Domain Machine Learning (MVFIF + CWT + MLSVD)	HC vs. LBBB vs. RBBB: Acc 99.88%; HC vs. BBB (binary): Acc 100%	Classification accuracy;	No hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power consumption, or model size) reported; no edge or wearable deployment discussed
[67]	RNN-based feature extraction with SOM feature selection + SVM classifier	Accuracy 99.4%; Sensitivity 99.8%; Specificity 99.0%; F1-score 99.4%	Accuracy; Sensitivity; Specificity; F1-score; mean p-value (Mann–Whitney U)	No hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power, model size) reported
[69]	CT-GAN with Gumbel SoftMax + conditional generation + 1-D CNN-based multi-class classifier	Acc 98.098% / 95.488% / 99.880%; F1 95.674% / 95.904% / 99.869%; class-wise ACC $\geq 97.45\%$ (UCI), $\geq 89.57\%$ (CINC), $\geq 97.95\%$	Accuracy; F1-score; Precision (PPV); Recall (TPR); TNR; NPV; FPR; FNR; FDR — reported per-class and averaged across majority, minority, and severe minority groups	Trained on Google Colab Pro with NVIDIA V100 (32 GB GPU); no hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power consumption, or model size) reported
[70]	Apple Watch Series 4 in 4-lead configuration (AW-4): standard wrist (lead I) + ankle (lead II) + two chest positions (pseudo-V1, pseudo-V6); physician-interpreted only — no automated algorithm evaluated beyond AF detection.	AW-4 physician interpretation: any abnormality Se 91%, AF Se 98%/Sp 97%, complete BBB Se 98%, AFL/AT Se 69%, ST/T abnormalities Se 77%, Q-waves Se 41%	Sensitivity, Specificity, PPV, NPV, Accuracy; McNemar’s test for AW-I vs AW-4 comparisons; physician consensus (3 cardiologists).	No automated algorithm evaluated for multi-lead configuration — all diagnostic performance reflects physician interpretation only. No edge hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power consumption, or model size) reported.
[71]	VAE - 1D residual CNN encoder–decoder with multi-head self-attention	MSe 0.00100, MAE: 0.01783, FID: 11.34; macro-AUROC 83.33% on MIMIC-IV; macro-AUROC 87.64% for regional MI localisation	MSE; MAE; FID; AUROC (per-condition and macro-averaged); blinded Turing test (3 cardiologists, $n = 50$)	Designed for 3-lead wearable input (II, V1, V5); no hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power, model size) reported.
[72]	3-lead ResNet + Transfer Learning with One-vs-All classification (3-lead input)	Micro-averaged F1 77% (vs. 78% for 12-lead baseline); only 1% below the 12-lead model despite 75% input reduction	Micro-averaged F1-score; Precision; Recall (per-class and global)	Designed for 3-lead wearable ECG (e.g., Apple Watch, KardiaMobile); no hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power, model size) reported

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Reference	Best Model	Best Model Scores	Evaluation Metrics	On-Edge Deployment Constraints
[73]	MuRe-LAT: Lead-Aware Multi-Resolution Transformer with domain-adaptive batch normalisation and masked self-supervised pretraining (12.3 M parameters)	MIT-BIH: Acc 94.0%, Macro-F1 88.4%, AUROC 96.2%, PR-AUC: 91.6%; PTB-XL: Acc 88.7%, Macro-F1 78.1%, AUROC 90.5%; cross-domain (PTB-XL→MIT-BIH): Acc 91.7%	Accuracy; Macro-F1; AUROC; PR-AUC; class-wise Precision, Recall, F1 (five AAMI classes); cross-domain generalisation accuracy	12.3 M parameters; 2.65 GFLOPs per 10 s window; inference latency 8.4 ms per 10 s input; no target hardware benchmarks reported; zero-padding used for 2-lead MIT-BIH inputs adds <3% FLOP overhead
[75]	ViT-B/384 (Vision Transformer, 86 M parameters, 384 × 384 px input, 12 transformer blocks, 12 attention heads)	Overall: Acc 96.79%, Pr: 96.79%, Re: 96.79%, F1 96.78%; class-wise: AFib 98.39%, GSVT 97.83%, SB 99.24%, SR 98.11%	Accuracy; Precision; Recall; F1-score (overall and per-class: AFib, GSVT, SB, SR); confusion matrix; six CAM methods compared qualitatively (EigenCAM, EigenGradCAM, GradCAM++, XGradCAM, LayerCAM, ScoreCAM)	Trained on NVIDIA RTX 4090 (64 GB RAM, Intel i9-14900K); no inference latency, power consumption, or model size for deployment reported; 86 M parameters preclude direct MCU/wearable deployment without compression; no edge hardware benchmarks provided
[76]	1-D Residual CNN	F1 >=80% across 6 abnormalities; Sp >99%, best single class: LBBB F1 1.000	Precision (PPV), Sensitivity, Specificity, F1-score, mAP, McNemar test, bootstrapped CIs	No hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power, model size) reported
[77]	1-D ResNet CNN	AUC ≥ 96% for 32/38 classes (84.2%); F1 81.2%	AUC (ROC); F1-score (frequency-weighted); Sensitivity; Specificity	No hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power, model size) reported
[79]	1D CNN using four wrist-worn ECG leads (I, V3-LA, V5-LA, A-LA) with Grad-CAM explainability	Se 77%; Sp 75% (all groups); Sp 0.94% when distinguishing AMI vs. healthy only	Sensitivity, Specificity, Area under ROC	No edge hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power consumption, or model size) reported.
[81]	2-D CNN-based AI-ECG tool (probability scores for qSTEMI, qACS, qMI)	qACS AUROC 98.7% (smart-watch) vs 99.1% (12-lead); P: 0.745; qSTEMI AUROC 98.2% vs 98.9%, P: 0.617; Spearman $\rho=0.88-0.89$ for all scores, all $P<0.001$	AUROC, Spearman correlation, Bland-Altman bias; benchmarked against 3-cardiologist expert consensus	No edge hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power consumption, or model size) reported.
[82]	Multi-branch LSTM	CinC 2021 challenge score: 0.486 ± 0.012 (5-fold CV); F1 31.4%	CinC 2021 normalised weighted challenge score; F1-measure; Precision; Recall; ROC, AUC	12-lead clinical ECG; no wearable or single-lead deployment; no hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power, model size) reported
[83]	QCG (Quantitative ECG) — 16-layer multi-channel CNN with non-local block	AUC: 94.7%; Se 98.1%; Sp 76.9%; PPV: 89.8%; NPV: 95.2%; non-inferior to joint EP+cardiologist evaluation.	AUC-ROC, Sensitivity, Specificity, PPV, NPV (95% CI); non-inferiority testing (5% margin); DeLong's method for AUC comparison; McNemar test.	No edge hardware benchmarks (inference latency, power consumption, or model size) reported.

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Reference	Best Model	Best Model Scores	Evaluation Metrics	On-Edge Deployment Constraints
[95]	Personalised HRV-based detection algorithm with smartphone-connected wearable ECG	Se 90.5%; GTCS sensitivity: 100%; false alarms median: 1.1/24h	Sensitivity; false alarm rate; consciousness assessment accuracy	Single-lead ECG streamed via Bluetooth to Android smartphone at 256 Hz; no hardware benchmarks (power, latency, model size) reported
On-Edge and Hardware-Constrained Deployment				
[24]	LEAF-Net (Lightweight Evolutionary Attention Fusion Network): hybrid 1D CNN-Transformer	ECG: Acc 95.7%, Se 97.8%, Sp 91.2%, F1 97%; PPG: Acc 96.9%, Se 97.4%, Sp 95.4%, F1 97.8%	Accuracy; Sensitivity; Specificity; PPV; F1-score; AUC; inference time (s/segment); FLOPS (Gmac); parameter count (M)	LEAF-N: 3.6 M parameters, 0.01 Gmac FLOPS, 0.18 s/segment inference; deployed on STM32L442KCU6 MCU with Bluetooth
[28]	DeepECG-Net (hybrid CNN + Transformer with multi-head self-attention)	Acc 98.2%; Pr: 98.2%; Re: 96.8%; F1 97.5%	Accuracy; Precision; Recall; F1-score	Model size 30 MB; inference latency <50 ms; deployed on Raspberry Pi 4B (4 GB RAM); extended with federated learning for distributed, privacy-preserving deployment
[50]	Lightweight CNN via knowledge distillation (12-lead teacher to single-lead student)	Acc 96.32%; model compression ratio: 1242.58×	Accuracy; model compression ratio; model size	STM32F429 (ARM Cortex-M4): 2 MB flash, 256 KB RAM, 180 MHz; deployed via STM32CubeAI; 1242.58× smaller than teacher model; battery-wearable-suitable
[56]	1-D CNN	Se 87%, Sp 96%, F1 82% on out-of-distribution subjects (segment-level, 10-s windows)	Sensitivity; Specificity; F1-score (segment-level)	Deployed on ZioXT single-lead ECG patch (iRhythm; 200 Hz, ~3.2 μ V resolution); 14-day continuous ambulatory monitoring; no inference latency or power benchmarks reported.
[61]	HRRCNN: 2D Conv blocks + dual-channel SE-ResNet (multi-scale spatial features) \rightarrow recombination \rightarrow Hybrid RNN (2-layer BiGRU 1-layer BiLSTM) + attention classifier;	Acc 95.08%; F1-macro: 87.22%; Se 88.51%; PPV: 86.13%	Accuracy; F1-macro; Sensitivity; PPV	Model deployed on a custom single-lead wearable device; no inference latency, power consumption, or model size reported for the embedded platform
[63]	Improved SVM with Minimum Description Length (MDL) feature selection	Acc 99.2%; Se 98.8%; Sp 99.5%; and a F1-score:98.9%	Accuracy, Sensitivity, Specificity and F1-score	Designed for implantable biomedical devices; low-power continuous monitoring; QRS extraction via wavelet transform; 12-feature HRV parameter set

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Reference	Best Model	Best Model Scores	Evaluation Metrics	On-Edge Deployment Constraints
[78]	1-D CNN Classification Coprocessor (configurable, multi-lead)	Acc >98%; Energy efficiency: 397.1 GOPS/W (>40% improvement over prior work)	Accuracy; Energy efficiency (GOPS/W); Power (nJ/op)	Fabricated in 55 nm CMOS; 62.2 nJ at 100 MHz; reconfigurable PE array; register-level data reuse; supports multiple lead configurations; updatable inference model
[84]	LSTM on custom 32-bit ARM Cortex-M PCB	Acc 98.1%; Se 98.2%; Sp 99.5%; F1 99.5%; R-peak error: 6.3 ms; latency: 20 ms/beat	Accuracy; Sensitivity; Specificity; F1-score; RPE (ms); inference latency	Custom PCB with 32-bit ARM Cortex-M; current draw 5.9 mA; beat-by-beat real-time processing (20 ms); fully on-device, no cloud dependency

Notes on Table 1:

- "Best model" refers to the top-performing architecture reported within each study; where multiple models were compared, only the best is listed.
- On-edge deployment constraints include: model size, inference latency, power consumption, target hardware (MCU, FPGA, Raspberry Pi, smartwatch), and signal-quality or architectural limitations specific to wearable deployment.
- Abbreviations: Se – Sensitivity; Sp – Specificity; Acc – Accuracy; AUROC – Area Under Receiver Operating Characteristic curve; F1 – F1-score; MAE – Mean Absolute Error; PPV – Positive Predictive Value; NPV – Negative Predictive Value; SNR – Signal-to-Noise Ratio; NMSE – Normalised Mean Squared Error; PCC – Pearson Correlation Coefficient; TPR/TNR – True Positive/Negative Rate; GOPS/W – Giga Operations Per Second per Watt; RPE – R-peak Position Error; MDL – Minimum Description Length; FOTDML – Fifth-Order Tensor Domain Machine Learning; CMA – Cross-Modal Attention; SQA – Signal Quality Assessment.

9.1 Signal quality assessment as a decision component

Classic feature-based SQA methods (Section 3.1) retain practical appeal for resource-constrained deployment: Abreu and Silva [30] demonstrate that eight handcrafted cardiac features suffice for reliable quality gating in a demanding firefighter scenario, achieving 88% accuracy, while Fu et al. [29] show that a compact set of entropy- and spectral-based features matches the performance of more complex pipelines on wearable recordings. These results challenge the implicit assumption that deep SQA architectures are uniformly superior, particularly in settings where interpretability and low compute are primary constraints. However, the advantage of deep methods becomes apparent in more demanding tasks: Mondal et al. [32] show that a CNN operating on the derivative ECG generalises to two entirely unseen databases — a generalisation property that rule-based or feature-threshold methods rarely demonstrate, as their parameters are typically tuned on specific acquisition environments.

A more fundamental disagreement concerns what SQA should output. Binary clean/noisy classification is the most common formulation, but Rakshit and Maity [34] demonstrate that a five-class taxonomy distinguishing noise type (low-, high-, mixed-frequency, and unacceptable) directly improves downstream denoising by enabling noise-specific processing — a finding that is logically compelling but has not yet been independently replicated on a different dataset. Kalouskova et al. [33] take a third position: fine-grained segment-level readability scoring, where the key clinical threshold (heart rate detectability) achieves 98.70% accuracy while the full four-class problem reaches only 87.62% — suggesting that the utility of fine-grained quality labels depends heavily on whether downstream tasks can exploit them.

A methodological concern that runs across all SQA studies is the inflation of reported metrics by aggressive signal rejection. When a quality gate discards a high proportion of segments, classification accuracy on the retained subset is not a meaningful estimate of system performance — yet the fraction of rejected segments and its downstream effect on diagnostic yield are rarely reported. Studies should report the acceptance rate alongside conditional accuracy, and evaluate how

performance degrades as the rejection threshold is relaxed. Without this, SQA benchmarks remain incomparable across publications and the clinical cost of quality-gating cannot be assessed.

9.2 *Single-lead interpretation: scale versus morphological limitations*

The reviewed literature does not consistently support the dominance of any single methodological paradigm for single-lead ECG interpretation. For rhythm tasks — particularly AF detection — deep discriminative models trained on large single-lead datasets show strong and consistent performance [52, 51], and Ribeiro et al. [76] demonstrate that a DNN trained on over two million 12-lead exams can reach or exceed the performance of cardiology residents. However, this evidence base rests heavily on large, carefully curated institutional datasets. When scale is limited, the picture changes: Marzoug et al. [36] find that a Random Forest trained on 47 single-lead ECG features in a cohort of 80 participants achieves only moderate performance for metabolic syndrome detection, substantially below what large-cohort deep learning studies typically report — a result that reflects cohort size as much as any intrinsic limitation of the feature-based approach.

The most direct evidence for a cross-paradigm comparison comes from studies that pit classical and deep methods against each other on the same dataset. Kilic et al. [64] find that LightGBM with morphological and HRV features outperforms a 1D CNN on arrhythmia classification from 3-channel Holter ECG — a result that runs counter to the general narrative of deep learning superiority. Conversely, Jančiulevičiūtė et al. [79] report that CNN outperforms a gradient-boosting decision tree for AMI detection from wrist-worn 4-lead ECG. These contradictory findings are not easily reconciled: task type, lead configuration, dataset size, and feature engineering quality all interact, and no reviewed study systematically isolates any one factor. The practical implication is that claiming architectural superiority based on any single study is not justified; the choice between paradigms should be guided by dataset properties and deployment constraints.

A persistent methodological problem in this literature is subject-level data leakage. When individual patients contribute multiple segments to both training and test sets, reported metrics overestimate generalisation. Meisenzahl et al. [56] explicitly enforce subject-level exclusion for out-of-distribution validation, which represents best practice, but many reviewed studies do not describe their split protocol with sufficient transparency to verify whether this source of inflation has been avoided. For morphology-rich diagnoses (ischaemia, bundle branch blocks, metabolic changes), where inter-subject ECG variability is high, this distinction is particularly consequential.

9.3 *Multi-lead interpretation and signal reconstruction validation*

Multi-lead analysis opens richer spatial information but does not automatically translate to superior outcome. Several studies reveal that the performance advantage of multi-lead over single-lead approaches is task-dependent and strongly modulated by architectural choices. Hughes et al. [77] demonstrate that a 38-class multi-label CNN trained on 12-lead data can achieve strong performance across five diagnostic categories, but this is contingent on having access to large-scale institutional labelled data, a resource unavailable in wearable contexts.

Signal reconstruction literature presents a more concerning pattern. Presacan et al. [43] report that their GAN-based 12-lead ECG reconstruction from single- or dual-lead input exhibits regression-to-the-mean behaviour — the model produces outputs that are statistically plausible at the population level but fail to reproduce patient-specific morphological detail. Adding a second input lead did not significantly improve reconstruction quality. Yoon et al. [40] similarly evaluate 12-lead reconstruction from lead I via a U-Net-based GAN, assessing feasibility through downstream tasks rather than direct morphological validation. Both studies illustrate the central risk of generative reconstruction: waveform similarity metrics (RMSE, PCC, SNR) can appear satisfactory while clinically critical features — ST deviations, T-wave polarity, QRS morphology — are poorly preserved. No reviewed reconstruction study validates reconstructed leads by the preservation of pathology-specific waveform features or by downstream diagnostic concordance in a patient cohort with confirmed disease, which should be regarded as a significant gap in the evidence base.

From a methodological standpoint, the dominant inflation risk in multi-lead studies is the use of single-institution datasets without external validation. Hughes et al. [77] note the role of LIME for identifying which ECG segments drive classification decisions — an important step toward clinical trust, but one that cannot substitute for independent cohort validation. Cross-paradigm comparison at the multi-lead level is further hindered by heterogeneous evaluation protocols: some studies report AUROC, others accuracy or F1, and lead configurations vary from 4-lead wrist-worn to full 12-lead clinical recordings, making aggregate conclusions unreliable without harmonised benchmarks.

9.4 Preprocessing standardisation and reporting

Preprocessing decisions are among the least standardised and least transparently reported aspects of wearable ECG pipelines, yet they have a direct bearing on reported performance. Reported high-pass cutoff frequencies vary from 0.05 Hz to 1.0 Hz across reviewed studies, window lengths range from 2 to 30 seconds, and normalisation strategies differ between amplitude scaling, z-score normalisation, and no normalisation. These choices are not cosmetic: altering the high-pass cutoff can suppress or preserve baseline wander that encodes respiratory information; window length determines the minimum detectable arrhythmia duration; and the absence of amplitude normalisation can introduce device-specific gain differences as a confounding feature.

A particular inflation risk arises when augmentation or synthetic signal generation is applied without careful separation from the test set. Liu et al. [24] synthesise noisy training samples using a parameterised noise injection formula — a principled approach, but one that requires verification that the synthetic noise distribution matches real wearable artefacts, which is not demonstrated. When synthetic samples inadvertently share statistical properties with real test data (e.g., through shared noise templates), augmentation inflates rather than improves generalisation. Similarly, Rahman et al. [84] demonstrate that beat windowing strategy interacts strongly with embedded hardware constraints and classification performance, yet few studies test robustness to plausible preprocessing variants. Preprocessing should be documented as a component of the method — with filter parameters, window definitions, normalisation choices, and augmentation protocols — and sensitivity analyses to key preprocessing decisions should be reported where feasible.

9.5 System-level evaluation of quality handling strategies

Reviewed studies treat quality handling as a preprocessing step rather than a system-level design decision, and this framing limits the evidence available for clinical translation. The filtering and rejection mechanisms described in Section 7 collectively determine diagnostic yield, alarm burden, and downstream model reliability — yet no reviewed paper evaluates these properties jointly. Jančiulevičiūtė et al. [79] discard beats above the 90th percentile of within-recording energy and require a minimum of 10 accepted beats, but do not report how frequently this threshold triggers full recording rejection or its effect on case coverage.

Synthetic signal generation for class balancing or robustness augmentation (Section 7.2) represents a specific quality-handling strategy with meaningful risks. The noise injection approach of Liu et al. [24] generates unacceptable-quality samples by combining clean ECG with scaled noise drawn from the MIT-BIH noise stress test database. While methodologically explicit, this approach assumes that the synthetic artefact distribution approximates the real wearable noise regime — an assumption that is plausible but not validated against device-acquired free-living recordings. If synthetic distributions diverge from real wearable conditions, the model may learn to identify synthetic artefacts rather than genuine quality degradation, producing an inflated SQA score on the training distribution. A system-level evaluation of quality handling should therefore report: (i) acceptance rate at each quality threshold, (ii) diagnostic yield per patient per monitoring period, (iii) alarm rate stratified by activity and device type, and (iv) performance on a held-out set containing exclusively real-world (non-synthetic) degraded signals.

9.6 Dataset representativeness and optimistic bias

The most consistent source of performance inflation across all reviewed paradigms is the use of non-representative training and evaluation data. Established benchmarks such as MIT-BIH and PTB-XL are systematically overrepresented in evaluation: they contain higher-quality signals, controlled acquisition conditions, and demographic profiles that differ materially from consumer wearable users in free-living environments. As visible in Table 1, a substantial proportion of reviewed studies validate exclusively or primarily on these benchmarks, making it impossible to determine whether reported performance generalises to the wearable context that motivates the work.

Novel datasets (Section 8.2) partially address this gap but introduce different concerns. The wECGdb [92] and ScientISST MOVE [31] datasets provide genuine wearable recordings, but they are small — 92 and 17 participants respectively — making them insufficient for training deep models without substantial augmentation or transfer learning, both of which introduce their own evaluation challenges. The Childhood Cancer Survivor dataset [90], with 243 participants, is larger but demographically specific; generalisability to the general population should not be assumed.

Several reviewed studies validate on proprietary institutional datasets without external validation, including Kilic et al. [64], who use a single-centre Holter archive available only from the corresponding author. While this data may be high quality, the absence of external validation means that the reported LightGBM versus CNN performance comparison cannot be attributed to the

architectural choice rather than to dataset characteristics. The appropriate response to this limitation is not to exclude internally validated studies from review, but to explicitly weight the strength of their evidence accordingly. Future work should prioritise subject-wise split protocols that are explicitly documented, evaluation on datasets that differ in acquisition device and demographic composition from the training set, and reporting of calibration and positive predictive value under realistic prevalence — not only sensitivity and specificity at a single operating point.

9.7 Outlook

The evidence reviewed here does not support a single architectural prescription for wearable ECG analysis: classical feature-based methods remain competitive for rhythm tasks under resource constraints [30, 29], while deep discriminative models show stronger cross-database generalisation when training data are sufficient [32, 76]. The most consistent finding is that dataset scale and representativeness explain more of the performance variance than architectural choice — a conclusion that has direct implications for how future progress should be measured and claimed.

The most impactful near-term advances are likely to come from three directions that are currently underinvested relative to architectural novelty: (i) rigorous evaluation protocols that enforce subject-level splits, report acceptance rates alongside conditional accuracy, and validate on genuinely wearable (not single-lead-extracted clinical) datasets; (ii) quality-aware inference pipelines in which SQA and diagnostic models are jointly optimised rather than sequentially stacked; and (iii) reconstruction and generation methods that are validated on clinically meaningful outcomes rather than waveform similarity metrics alone. Until these evaluation standards become normative, performance comparisons across studies will remain unreliable, and the gap between published results and real-world deployability will persist.

10 Conclusion

This review examined machine learning methods for automated wearable ECG analysis, covering signal quality assessment, single-lead and multi-lead interpretation, preprocessing pipelines, and quality handling strategies. Eighteen datasets were described — six established open-access benchmarks and twelve novel datasets, the majority providing genuine wearable recordings — to document the data conditions under which reviewed methods were developed and evaluated. The review reveals a field with substantial methodological diversity and rapid growth, but also with recurring evaluation weaknesses that limit the interpretability of reported results.

Across all three problem domains, no single architectural paradigm consistently outperforms others when studies are compared fairly. Classical feature-based methods remain competitive for rhythm classification under resource constraints and in small-cohort settings; deep discriminative models demonstrate stronger cross-database generalisation when training data are sufficient; attention-based and generative architectures offer promising capabilities for sequence modelling and signal reconstruction, but their practical utility is currently limited by the absence of task-appropriate validation. The most consistent predictor of reported performance is dataset characteristics — particularly scale, demographic composition, and whether signals were acquired from wearable devices in free-living conditions or extracted as a single lead from clinical 12-lead recordings — rather than architectural choice.

Three specific evaluation deficiencies recur across the literature and should be addressed in future work. First, subject-level data leakage in train/test splits inflates classification metrics; future studies should document split protocols explicitly and report performance on strictly held-out subjects. Second, SQA performance is routinely reported as conditional accuracy on accepted segments without disclosing the acceptance rate, making it impossible to assess the clinical cost of quality-gating; both figures should be reported together. Third, reconstructed or synthesised ECG leads are evaluated by waveform similarity metrics alone; future reconstruction studies should additionally validate by preservation of pathology-specific features — ST deviations, QRS morphology, T-wave polarity — and by downstream diagnostic concordance in cohorts with confirmed disease.

A structured evaluation framework for wearable ECG methods should therefore include: signal input quality as a covariate in all performance analyses; explicit reporting of model size, inference latency, and target hardware for any study claiming edge deployability; subject-wise generalisation as a required evaluation condition rather than an optional supplement; and validation on datasets acquired from the target wearable device under representative free-living conditions. Datasets that satisfy these requirements remain scarce, and their systematic development represents the single highest-impact investment the wearable ECG community can make to accelerate clinically meaningful progress.

Author contributions

B.P.: Conceptualisation; literature search; writing—original draft; writing—review and editing.

Conflict of Interest

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